

Decentring the Study of Migrant
Returns and Return Policies

Country Dossier GREECE

WP7: Return Aspirations and Trajectories of Migrants

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List of abbreviations

AVRR	Assisted Voluntary Return and Reintegration
CCAC	Closed Controlled Access Centres
EU	European Union
GAS	Greek Asylum Service
IOM	International Organization for Migration
MMA	Ministry of Migration and Asylum
OCAVRR	Open Centre for migrants registered for Assisted Voluntary Return and Reintegration
PRDC	Pre-Removal Detention Center
RIC	Reception and Identification Center
RMI	Return Migration Infrastructure
TCN	Third-country national

Summary

This Country Dossier focusing on Greece is part of Work Package 7 of the GAPs project. It examines migrants' experiences in Greece, both as a settlement and transit country, focusing on shifting aspirations, social integration, and mobility decisions, especially as regards the 'pre-return phase'. The 'pre-return phase' is perceived broadly, to include migrants who are found in the 'spectrum of risk of return', including those who are at close or mid-term risk of return, either today or in the near future. Moreover, recognising that return is part of complex, non-linear migration trajectories, the dossier also highlights patterns such as onward movements, re-orientations, periods of rest, and intermediate settlements. These trajectories include multiple returns to countries of origin, re-migration to Greece, or circular migration. Migrants' return experiences encompass both forced and assisted voluntary returns, viewed as part of a continuum of coercion rather than a strict dichotomy.

The Dossier, first, examines migrants' agency in their movements and the reasons behind them, including not only migration to Greece but also their complex and non-linear trajectories. Second, it investigates the integration context in Greece, focusing on issues related to economic and labour precarity, housing instability, processes of irregularisation, institutional racism, policing, deportability, and the barriers to accessing essential services. It argues that the social and economic context of settlement and integration in Greece, as determined also by the governance of migration, both has affected previous mobilities and impacts on perceptions and future aspirations. Third, the Country Dossier analyses social networks, family and institutions by focusing on the neighbourhood level (though not exclusively) to shed light on relationships ranging from mutual care and racism, on the importance of friends and family and on migrants' involvement in migrant communities and other political organisations. Fourth, it discusses migrants' perceptions of returning to their country of origin, followed by their views on the possibility of migrating elsewhere. Importantly, a range of mixed drivers of return decision emerge, including irregularisation and the non-possession of a stable and long term legal status, the employment precarity and labour exploitation, health issues and physical exhaustion among others. Finally, the Country Dossier proposes a flexible typology of migration trajectories, grounded in the research findings and shaped by the prevailing social, political, and economic conditions in Greece.

The findings are based on both desk research and primary research involving 30 interviews with migrants who are found in the broad 'spectrum of risk of return' either today or in the near future. The interview sample included participants currently holding regular status after experiences of irregularisation in the past, as well as irregularised migrants, including long-settled ones, people who have recently arrived and remained irregularised, and rejected asylum seekers from countries with 'low recognition rates'. Field research also included several ethnographic tools such as field visits, observations and guided tours in different places in Athens.

The GAPs Project

GAPs is a Horizon Europe project that aims to conduct a comprehensive multidisciplinary study on the drivers of return policies and the barriers and enablers of international cooperation on return migration. The overall aim of the project is to examine the disconnects and discrepancies between expectations of return policies and their actual outcomes by de-centring the dominant, one-sided understanding of 'return policymaking'. To this end, GAPs:

- examine the shortcomings of EU's return governance;
- analyse enablers and barriers to international cooperation, and
- explore the perspectives of migrants themselves to understand their knowledge, aspirations and experiences with return policies.

GAPs combines its decentring approach with three innovative concepts:

- a focus on return migration infrastructures, which allows the project to analyse governance fissures;
- an analysis of return migration diplomacy to understand how relations between EU Member States and with third countries hinder cooperation on return; and
- a trajectory approach that uses a socio-spatial and temporal lens to understand migrant agency.

GAPs is an interdisciplinary 3-year project (2023-2026), co-coordinated by Uppsala University and the Bonn International Centre for Conflict Studies with 17 partners in 12 countries on 4 continents. GAPs' fieldwork has been conducted in 12 countries: Sweden, Nigeria, Germany, Morocco, the Netherlands, Afghanistan, Poland, Georgia, Turkey, Tunisia, Greece and Iraq.

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1. Introduction

This Country Dossier of Greece is part of Work Package (WP) 7 of the GAPs ‘De-centring the Study of Migrant Returns and Readmission Policies in Europe and Beyond’¹ project. WP7 aims to explore how migrants consider, decide, and perceive return decisions during the ‘pre-return phase’, situating these within broader im/mobility experiences.

The Dossier examines migrants’ experiences in Greece, both as a settlement and transit country, focusing on their shifting aspirations, social integration, and mobility decisions, especially as regard the ‘pre-return phase’. The ‘pre-return phase’ is perceived broadly, to include migrants who are found in the ‘spectrum of risk of return’, including those who are at close or mid-term risk of return, either today or in the near future. Recognising that return is part of complex, non-linear migration trajectories, the dossier also highlights patterns such as onward movements, re-orientations, periods of rest, and intermediate settlements. These trajectories include multiple returns to countries of origin, re-migration to Greece, or circular migration. Migrants’ return experiences encompass both forced and assisted voluntary returns, viewed as part of a continuum of coercion rather than a strict dichotomy (Sahin-Mencutek and Triandafyllidou, 2024; Papatzani et al., forthcoming). The dossier also examines the influence of social networks and relationships on migration paths, alongside the impact of Greece’s integration and settlement context, including states of ‘limbo’ and irregularisation. Finally, it explores how these factors intersect with migrant agency to shape mobility decisions.

More particularly, the Dossier examines migrants’ agency in their movements and the reasons behind them, including not only migration to Greece but also their complex and non-linear trajectories. Second, it investigates the integration context in Greece, focusing on issues related to economic and labour precarity, housing instability, processes of irregularisation, institutional racism, policing, deportability, and the barriers to accessing essential services. It argues that the social and economic context of settlement and integration in Greece, as determined also by the governance of migration, both has affected previous mobilities and impacts on perceptions and future aspirations. Third, the Country Dossier analyses social networks, family and institutions by focusing on the neighbourhood level (though not exclusively) to shed light on relationships ranging from mutual care and racism, on the importance of friends and family and on migrants’ involvement in migrant communities and other political organisations. Fourth, it discusses migrants’ perceptions of returning to their country of origin, followed by their views on the possibility of migrating elsewhere. Importantly, a range of mixed drivers of return decision emerge, including irregularisation and the non-possession of a stable and long term legal status, employment precarity and labour exploitation, health issues and physical exhaustion among others. Finally, the Country Dossier proposes a flexible typology of migration trajectories, grounded in the research findings and shaped by the prevailing social, political, and economic conditions in Greece.

¹For more information, see: <https://www.returnmigration.eu/about>

2. Methods

Work Package 7 as a whole employed a combination of anthropological and sociological methods to examine migration dynamics among migrants. In Greece, the desk research benefited from previous country dossiers and working papers of GAPs project, particularly i) the Country Dossier on the legal framework of returns in Greece in the context of WP2 (Hatziprokopiou et al., 2024), ii) the Working Paper on issues of irregularisation in the context of WP2 (Papatzani et al., 2024), and iii) the Country Dossier on the Return Migration Infrastructures (RMIs) with a special focus on the Assisted Voluntary Return and Reintegration (AVRR) program implemented by the International Organization for Migration (IOM) in the context of WP3 (Papatzani et al., forthcoming).

The primary research involved both fieldwork and interviews, specifically 30 semi-structured interviews conducted with migrants between January and October 2024. Selected interviewees are migrants who are found in the broad ‘spectrum of risk of return’, including those who are at close or mid-term risk of return, either today or in the near future. The research targeted individuals with multiple and complex migration trajectories, such as first-time migration to Greece, return to their country of origin, and subsequent re-migration to Greece or other circular trajectories. Selection criteria did not focus solely on nationality or legal status but considered a combination of these factors, as well as specific periods of arrival and settlement in Greece, with an emphasis on those at ‘risk of return’. Flexibility guided both participant selection and the interpretation of categories like ‘forced’ or ‘voluntary’ return, aligning with the argument that these should be viewed as a continuum of coercion rather than as binary opposites (Papatzani et al., forthcoming).

The study included 14 interviews with migrants holding regular status: nine with residence permits in Greece, three with Greek citizenship (with former experiences of irregularisation, thus under the risk of return in the past), and one with an expatriate identity card. Additionally, 16 interviews were conducted with migrants in irregular status, including individuals whose international protection claims had been rejected². Among those with irregular status, six were long-settled migrants, primarily Georgian women who have worked as undeclared domestic workers in Greece for decades (one since 1989). Despite having had some form of documentation in the past, they are now undocumented and at risk of return, reflecting a common pattern of irregularisation for migrants who settled in Greece before 2015. The remaining ten arrived more recently (post-2016) and are also undocumented, often following asylum claim rejections and accompanying return orders. Many in this group are Pakistani migrants, a population facing low recognition rates. Three individuals in this category had applied for residence permits under new legislation introduced in Greece in late 2022. Finally, one interview was conducted with an asylum seeker.

The interviews included participants from various nationalities: nine from Pakistan, six from Georgia, three from Albania, two from Iraq (including one Kurd), two from Moldova, and one each from Afghanistan, Bangladesh, Egypt, Lebanon (Palestinian), Iran, India, Burundi, and the Philippines. Regarding gender, 11 participants were women, 18 were men, and one identified as queer. The sample consisted exclusively of adults (18+), with ages ranging from 20 to 78, ensuring a broad age representation. Additional selection criteria included diversity

²In the country dossier we often use the terms ‘migrants’, ‘refugees’ and ‘asylum seekers’ interchangeably, since we consider the movement of refugees as part of the wider migratory phenomenon. Thus, we do not necessarily follow the legal categories when describing the migration and return governance system as the aim of the dossier is not the legal analysis. Yet, when the term asylum seeker is used, we aim to refer to the particular legal category employed by the asylum system.

in employment status, education level, social class, and family circumstances, recognising the impact of these factors on return intentions.

Of the 30 interviews, 13 were conducted with people registered in the Assisted Voluntary Return and Reintegration (AVRR) program in Greece, either during the time of the research or in the past. Ten of them were conducted with AVRR returnees residing at the Open Centre for migrants registered for AVRR (OCAVRR) in Athens. This group included four Pakistanis—the second-largest nationality returning through AVRR, according to IOM statistics—with the remainder from Georgia, the Philippines, Burundi, India, Lebanon, and a Kurdish individual from Iraq. These participants primarily represented individuals who had ‘voluntarily’ chosen to return, placing them outside the typical ‘risk of return’ spectrum. However, they were included based on the researchers’ interpretation of voluntary return as part of a continuum of coercion. Additionally, one interview was conducted with a migrant enrolled in AVRR but not residing at OCAVRR at the time of the research, one with a migrant already returned to Georgia through AVRR, and another with a migrant that returned to Georgia through AVRR in the past, but later came back to Greece again.

Notably, 12 of the 30 participants had previously returned to countries of origin at least once, after their initial settlement in Greece, while some of them followed multiple or circular migration patterns. Few participants had also undertaken temporary migration journeys to other EU countries in the past, some of them potentially subject to Dublin returns³.

The research deliberately included participants from a broad range of arrival periods: early arrivals (spanning the 1990s to 2015/2016) and late arrivals (post-2015/2016). Early arrivals are often more established, potentially having severed ties with their home countries, while late arrivals may still contemplate return. Early arrivals may also have faced complex processes of irregularisation, leading to precarious legal statuses that place them within the spectrum of return risk. Some early arrivals may have experienced prior return trajectories before re-migrating to Greece. This flexible and open temporal framework allows the study to capture diverse cases, enriching the analysis. Additionally, key events in 2015-2016—such as the closure of the Balkan Route, the EU-Turkey Statement, and the implementation of the EU Hotspot Approach—marked significant milestones that shaped Greece’s legal and policy landscape. These events have had profound impacts on migrants’ and refugees’ movements, trajectories, experiences, motivations, and aspirations, further contextualising the study’s findings.

Most interviews were conducted in person in Athens, in various locations such as the neighbourhoods where migrants reside, their workplaces, coffee shops, the Open School for Migrants in Piraeus, and the EKKE offices in central Athens. Ten interviews took place at the OCAVRR. Additionally, three interviews were conducted online: one with a Georgian returnee and two with Pakistani migrants living on Greek islands and working seasonally in tourism.

Most interviewees were approached through the research team’s personal networks, while others were referred by the Open School for Migrants in Piraeus, the Athens Georgia House, and the Albanian Immigrants and Solidarity Initiative. Researchers followed an interview guide developed by WP7 leaders, structured to facilitate mapping migrant trajectories and examining agency, governance, networks, and integration contexts. The guide provided four primary questions with optional sub-questions, ensuring a clear focus while allowing flexibility in the interviews. All participants were provided with an Information Letter and gave either

³Individuals returning to Greece mainly from Northern European countries under Dublin III procedures are not included in the research and the targeted sample, as in the context of GAPs, Greece is mainly examined as a country returning migrants to countries of origin. Yet this remains a crucial issue to be investigated in future research.

written or oral consent to participate. Interviews were recorded with participant permission, securely stored, and deleted after transcription. The interviews were conversational in nature, typically lasting about an hour. Ethical considerations included ensuring anonymity and excluding sensitive questions when necessary. The names of the interviewees used in the Country Dossier are pseudonyms.

In addition to the interviews, the research also included ethnographic methods, particularly, i) visit, observation and interview contacts at the celebration of the Athens Georgia House in a central neighbourhood of Athens on March 2024, ii⁴) a guided tour at OCAVRR where interviews with AVRR & OCAVRR participants took place; iii) an observation of a departure of Georgian AVRR returnees at the El. Venizelos Athens International Airport.

When needed, necessary permissions (for the interviews and the field-visits) were granted by IOM and MMA, as the operating and the supervising authority for AVRR program in Greece, respectively. Overall, IOM's assistance was crucial for implementing part of the research. Their professional collaboration and willingness to contribute to our research set up the field and became an invaluable source of data.

⁴The guided tour at OCAVRR and the observation at the Airport also form part of the ethnographic methods of WP3 research.

3. Context

3.1 The historical background of the arrival and reception of migrants in the country

Greece has been both a destination and transit country for migrants over the past few decades. In the 1990s, it emerged as a migrant destination country, primarily due to migrant arrivals from the Balkans and Eastern Europe, particularly Albania. During this period, Greece lacked a comprehensive immigration policy, resulting in heavy policing, mass deportations, stringent legal residence requirements, regularisation procedures⁵, and widespread exploitation of migrant labour (Baldwin-Edwards & Fakiolas, 1998; Hatziprokopiou, 2006; Kandyliis, 2006). Since the late 1990s onward, with the upcoming 2004 Olympic Games as a catalyst, Greece implemented large-scale regularisation measures to secure the legal status of many undocumented migrants. Migrants, especially in sectors like construction, agriculture, and domestic services, played a key role in driving the country's high economic growth during that period. In the early 2000s, migrants from the Middle East, Africa, and Asia began arriving, some intending to settle and others using Greece as a transit point to reach other European countries. To this day, Pakistanis remain a significant portion of Greece's migrant population. Indicatively, in January 2024, Albanians were still the majority of third country nationals (TCNs) with valid residence permits in Greece (279,201 out of the total 472,062) while Pakistanis were in the third position (after China) with 19,509 migrants with valid residence permits (MMA, 2024).

Following the economic collapse in 2009, amidst a severe recession, austerity measures, rising unemployment, and increasing inequalities, an uncertain number of established migrants with varying legal statuses began leaving Greece spontaneously due to limited employment opportunities. For many, this resulted in repatriation, particularly among migrants from neighbouring countries such as Albania or Bulgaria, where circular migration patterns—often linked to seasonal work in agriculture and tourism—became more common. At the same time, the deteriorating living conditions in Greece were exploited to fuel racist rhetoric and discrimination against migrants.

Before 2015, and especially prior to 2011 when the Asylum Service was established, Greece lacked an effective mechanism to address the needs of asylum seekers and refugees and the Greek asylum system faced substantial criticism on multiple fronts (Tramountanis, 2023). The majority of asylum applications in the country were rejected at the first instance. Most migrants sought residence permits within a restrictive legal framework that made it difficult to obtain stable legal status. Residence permits were often renewed at a significant economic cost and sometimes even granted after their expiration. Long queues of individuals waiting to submit applications or receive documents from various authorities were common (Kandyliis, Papatzani, and Polyzou, 2024). For many, temporality and precarity defined their legal status over time, leading to cycles of 'regularity' and 'irregularity.' These dynamics highlighted 'irregularisation' as an ongoing process, rather than a fixed state, in which many individuals, even those with regular status, could become subjected in sequences of (ir)regular statuses (Papatzani et al., 2024).

In 2015, Greece became a key entry point to Europe for nearly one million migrants from Syria, Afghanistan, Iraq, and other countries, in what was widely referred to as a 'refugee crisis'.

⁵The first coordinated regularisation procedure was launched in 1998 under Presidential Decrees 358/1997 and 359/1997.

Following the implementation of the EU Hotspot approach, the closure of the Western Balkan Route, and the EU-Turkey Statement, many asylum seekers were forced to remain in Greece for extended periods. By the summer of 2016, the Greek Asylum Service (GAS) estimated that approximately 27,600 people were still on the mainland, intending to apply for asylum, as most of the one million migrants who had passed through Greece between 2015 and 2016 had already left the country (Tramountanis, 2023). Asylum applications became the primary means of regularisation. According to Figure 1, the main countries of origin of asylum applicants in 2022 were Afghanistan, Syria, Pakistan, Palestine, and Iraq, with Pakistanis having notably low recognition rates.

Figure 1. Main nationalities of asylum applicants in 2022.

Source: RSA, 2023.

A reception and temporary accommodation system was established due to Greece's obligation to asylum applicants' reception, according to EU Reception Conditions Directive. The enactment of a new reception law in 2016 introduced three main categories of institutional accommodation for asylum seekers: a) Reception and Identification Centers (RICs) (commonly referred to as 'hotspots') and Closed Controlled Access Centres (CCACs) located on eastern border islands and the land border near the Evros River, b) Open Temporary Reception Facilities, consisting of remote, often segregated camps or camp-like structures on the mainland, which gradually expanded, and are mostly remote and isolated facilities, characterized by containment, control, exclusion, and marginalisation of their residents (Papatzani et al., 2022a; 2022b); and c) the ESTIA housing program, which provided urban apartments for the most vulnerable asylum seekers and applicants for family reunification that was terminated in late 2022.

Since their establishment, these accommodation types have undergone significant changes in their locations, capacities, and operational methods. For example, in March 2022, there

were 24 mainland camps offering a total of 24,237 places (IOM, 2022), compared to 32 camps providing 30,520 places in December 2020 (IOM, 2020). As for ESTIA, in late 2020 it included 28,726 places in 4,576 apartments all over Greece (56% in Athens) (UNHCR, 2020), while one year later the accommodation places were reduced to 16,875 in 2,755 apartments, 65% of them located in Athens (MMA, 2022) and the program was terminated altogether in 2022. The features of these accommodation types have significantly influenced the living conditions and experiences of asylum applicants, highlighting their varying impacts on individuals' accommodation and overall quality of life (Papatzani et al., 2022a).

At the same time, the tightening of asylum procedures, including measures such as the safe third country concept and safe countries of origin, coupled with a lack of integration opportunities, has led to multiple aspects of irregularisation, even for asylum seekers. This has prompted many recognized refugees and asylum seekers in Greece to migrate further. Many, including those granted international protection, choose to leave Greece irregularly for other European countries offering better conditions. While some wait to complete the asylum process before leaving, others depart earlier (Papatzani et al., 2022b). This results in irregular status in their new destinations, due to the Dublin Regulation, which links asylum claims to the first country of entry, and limits recognized refugees to three-month visits to other EU countries. However, there have been institutional pathways for refugees to resettle in other EU countries, citing poor living conditions in Greece, supported by court rulings like the 2011 *M.S.S. v. Belgium and Greece* judgment⁶. For others, who do not manage to stay abroad, returning in Greece (especially after the reinstatement of internal Schengen border controls as the German government recently announced) comes together with a new risk of return, as many of them have not renewed the asylum status they received in Greece in the past or await a long time for the renewal, and therefore become irregularised (RSA & PRO ASYL, 2024a; 2024b).

The complexity of the asylum system and strict deterrence policies in Greece often lead some migrants to avoid applying for asylum altogether. To evade arrest and fingerprinting, they opt to remain undocumented, especially in urban centers, while planning their next move (Papatzani et al., 2022b). This self-irregularised status exposes them to the constant fear of police checks, detention, and possible deportation, as they navigate daily life focused on leaving the country.

In recent years, two legal arrangements have been introduced to respond to existing labour shortages in specific industries. The first is the Memorandum of Understanding on 'Immigration and Mobility' signed between Greece and Bangladesh, ratified by Law 4959/2022. This Memorandum establishes the conditions for entry and temporary residence for Bangladeshi nationals who were in Greece before February 9, 2022, for temporary employment. The residence permit is valid for five years, requires holders to return to Bangladesh for at least three months per year, and cannot be renewed or extended after its expiration. This law has regularized approximately 11,000 irregular workers, primarily in the agricultural sector, addressing exploitation issues, such as the Manolada incident (Kerasiotis, 2024). Additionally, in 2023, Greece and Egypt signed an agreement ratified by Law 5009/2023 to employ seasonal workers in the agricultural sector. The second legal measure is Law 5078/2023 (Article 193), which grants a new type of residence permit for work, effectively offering broad regularisation for undocumented migrants. This three-year permit requires proof of at least three years prior residence in Greece and a job offer by an employer. The permit can be renewed or converted into another type of residence permit.

⁶e.g. <https://www.courthousenews.com/refugees-cannot-be-returned-to-greece-german-court-rules>

Pragmatic labour market considerations seem to be at the heart of these recent legal initiatives, following about a decade of policies aimed primarily at regulating asylum and building a reception system at the expense of established migrants and their offspring (Christopoulos, 2020). Our interviews revealed, on the one hand, that a number of asylum seekers whose applications have been rejected, especially from nationalities with 'low recognition rates' (e.g. Pakistan), apply for residence permit through the new legislation, giving an end –at least temporarily (until the decision on their application)– to their irregular status that followed the rejection of their asylum claim. On the other, the implementation of these measures has faced challenges due to inconsistent interpretations of the law by immigration services. For example, undocumented migrants are required to present a rent contract, even though the Immigration Code prohibits contracts for TCNs without legal documents. Additionally, proof of uninterrupted three-year residence is often rejected by decentralized administrations, despite the law's flexibility and the lack of documentation among undocumented individuals. Such administrative barriers risk excluding many, limiting the benefits of regularisation (Kerasiotis, 2024).

3.2 The migration and return governance system

The concept of a 'multifaceted labyrinth', as described by Tsitselikis (2019) in relation to the Greek asylum system post-2015 also applies to the broader immigration regime, including the governance of returns and the development of Return Migration Infrastructures (Papatzani et al., forthcoming).

In the 1990s, Greece experienced mass deportations to Albania, often carried out on the periphery or in violation of official legal frameworks (Baldwin-Edwards & Fakiolas, 1998; Maroukis, 2008). These deportations were frequently the result of the notorious 'sweep operations' conducted by the police, aimed at combating irregular migration and its perceived link to criminal activity (Pavlou, 2009; Baldwin-Edwards, 2014).

By the mid-2000s, with the implementation of the Dublin II regulation, the number of individuals stranded in Greece increased, prompting the introduction of policies aimed at both preventing entry and facilitating return. These included the securitisation of borders, such as the adoption of the 'Integrated Border Management Program for Combating Illegal Immigration' in 2011, leading to the construction of the Evros fence along Greece's north-eastern border, framed as a 'technical barrier' to curb 'illegal' migration (Ministry of Citizen Protection, 2011). Additionally, the police launched the 'Xenios Zeus' operation in urban centers between 2012 and 2013, which involved patrols and violent raids intended to arrest and deport irregular migrants (Pavlou, 2009; Karamanidou, 2016). As documented, the operation, marked by its racialized nature, resulted in numerous human rights violations and an increase in detentions, rather than effectively identifying irregular migrants (HRW, 2012; 2013).

During this period, there have been several significant developments in Greece's migration management. Frontex began operating at both the land (Evros) and sea (Aegean) borders. The International Organization for Migration (IOM) launched the Assisted Voluntary Return and Reintegration (AVRR) program in 2010, and a system of Pre-Removal Detention Centres (PRDCs) was established, regulating already existing detention facilities. Additionally, in 2011, the Return Directive 2008/115/EC was incorporated into Greek law (Law 3907/2011), outlining the procedures for returns, without replacing Law 3386/2005, which addressed administrative expulsion (deportations). The coexistence of these two laws has created

ambiguity and complexity in the legal framework, and although Law 4825/2021 aimed to clarify their scope, it has not fully resolved the inconsistencies (Hatziprokopiou et al., 2024).

In response to the 2015 refugee movement, the EU-Turkey Statement, which served as a return agreement, stipulated that migrants and asylum seekers with unfounded or inadmissible claims would be ‘returned’ from Greece to Turkey. While the implementation of this agreement led to a decrease in departures from Turkey, it did not result in a significant increase in the actual number of returns. Furthermore, since 2019, there has been a notable rise in reported pushbacks at both land and sea borders (BVMN, 2020; Greek Ombudsman, 2023), which has effectively become a ‘de facto general policy’ (United Nations, General Assembly, 2022), despite Greek government claims that these allegations are ‘clearly unfounded’ (MMA, 2021). The recently established Recording Mechanism of Informal Forced Returns has recorded a total number of alleged victims of at least 2,157 people from April 2020 to October 2022 (GNCHR, 2023), and a minimum number of 1,438 alleged victims between January 2022 and December 2023 from countries whose nationals are granted international protection status in Greece and the rest of the EU at significant rates (GNCHR, 2024).

The further institutionalisation of returns was marked by the creation of the Directorate of Returns and Withdrawals in 2020, followed by the appointment of a National Coordinator of Returns within the MMA in late 2023 (Hatziprokopiou et al., 2024). Additionally, the ‘Joint Reintegration Services’ program was launched in August 2023, funded by and in collaboration with Frontex (Papatzani et al., forthcoming). This program involves return counsellors who inform potential returnees in Pre-Removal Detention Centres (PRDCs) about the program and its provisions.

In terms of data, it is important to mention that the number of third-country nationals (TCNs) ‘found to be illegally present’ in Greece ranged from approximately 40,000 to slightly over 100,000 for most of the period from 2008 to 2023, with one notable exception in 2015-2016. The number of TCNs ordered to leave showed a sharp increase after 2015 and then a decline over 2020-23, with an exception in 2022. The number of those who actually returned following a return order represents a steady minority among those receiving such an order (Hatziprokopiou et al., 2024). Eurostat data suggest an overall decline in the number of returns, from over 19,000 in 2016-17 to about just above 7,000 in 2021-22. Forced returns as a share of the total have also declined, while voluntary returns have increased: the proportion of forced returns was reduced from 68-70% of total returns in 2016-17, to 47.7% in 2021 and 38.2% in 2022. In 2023, 29,869 removal orders were issued by the Hellenic Police (in comparison with roughly 30,600 in 2022 and 21,000 in 2021): about two out of three returns were based on Law 3907/2011 (transposing the Return Directive), and one out of three were based on Law 3386/2005 (on administrative expulsions), in derogation from the Return Directive (RSA, 2024). As regards detention, a key aspect of the forced removal infrastructure, in 2023 alone, the Hellenic Police issued more than 24,000 detention orders, 10,000 under Law 3907/2011, roughly the same number under Law 3386/2005 and 3,600 in the asylum process (RSA, 2024).

The main nationalities of those receiving a return decision are Albania (17%), Pakistan (17%), Syria (12%), Afghanistan (10%), and Iraq (8%). Concerning migrants who did ‘return’ to another country during the same period, either by a forced return operation, an assisted ‘voluntary’ return operation, or a non-assisted one, the main countries of citizenship include Albania (51%), Pakistan (11%), Georgia (10%), and Iraq (7%). Albanians, who constitute the largest and most established migrant group in Greece, also make up the majority of those returned to their country of origin. While most of these ‘irregular’ Albanian migrants are apprehended for illegal entry, they are predominantly arrested in inland areas. In 2020, for

example, 651 out of a total of 2,877 returned Albanian nationals were repatriated under simplified readmission procedures (RSA, 2020). It is likely that many of those returned, including some Albanian migrants, are not newcomers, but rather individuals who have lived in Greece for varying periods, potentially engaging in circular migration between Greece and Albania without obtaining or renewing a legal migration status⁷. Furthermore, migrants from other third countries, including those from Syria, Afghanistan, Palestine, and Iran—despite often having high recognition rates for international protection—are also frequently identified as ‘illegally present’ and subsequently ordered to leave, despite the practical challenges in executing their return (Papatzani et al., 2024).

Assisted ‘voluntary’⁸ return through the IOM’s AVRR program appear to have proportionally increased (e.g. over 40% of total returns in the last couple of years as compared to about 30% in 2016-17), yet the number of beneficiaries in 2022 was 3,065, about half that in 2016, and far lower than in the early years of the programme (more than 9,320 migrants participated in 2013, over 7,350 in 2014) (IOM, 2024a: 5). In 2023, 2,705 migrants participated in AVRR, making up 42.7% of total returns. Returnees of the 2019-23 programme were in their majority nationals of Georgia (37%), Pakistan (23%) and Iraq (13%) - a composition somewhat less diverse compared to 2016-19, when the principal origin countries were Pakistan (26.3%), Iraq (25%), Georgia (12%), Afghanistan (8%) and Algeria (8%). The current programme aims to return 17,000 individuals in a period of 52 months, to elaborate 1,700 reintegration plans and to provide accommodation for 1,700 individuals in OCAVRR.

Finally, pushbacks from Greece have been a well-known practice for over three decades (Karamanidou and Kasperek, 2022; GNCHR, 2023; 2024). The recently established Recording Mechanism of Informal Forced Returns has recorded a total number of alleged victims of at least 2,157 people from April 2020 to October 2022 (GNCHR, 2023), and a minimum number of 1,438 alleged victims between January 2022 and December 2023 from countries whose nationals are granted international protection status in Greece and the rest of the EU at significant rates (GNCHR, 2024).

3.3 The development of ‘return migration discourses’

In Greece, the emergence of ‘return migration discourses’ is closely tied to the country’s role within transnational migration dynamics and the socio-economic and political pressures faced by both migrants and the host society. Discourses on return migration have been influenced by particular political circumstances that can be categorised mainly to the period of the 1990s, the early 2000s, the post-2008 debt crisis, and the post-2015 ‘refugee crisis’. An extensive discussion of the particular social, economic and /or political conditions and/or incidents that influenced the different dominant discourses on migration and returns, during each one of these periods, is out of the scope of the Country Dossier. Two milestones should be discussed, though, under the general understanding that return migration is often promoted as a ‘practical’ solution to irregular migration coupled not only with official return policies, but also

⁷ Eurostat data remain silent about the period of stay or the date of arrival of the apprehended and the ‘returned’ in a MS. Failing to collect such information, individual trajectories prior to apprehension or return are effectively effaced.

⁸ ‘Voluntary’ return is depicted in two categories, the assisted and the non-assisted. As regards the latter, it was recorded in 2019, labelled (non-assisted) ‘voluntary’ (‘ουκαιοθελής’ in Greek), which remains fairly low but is on the rise (Hatziprokopiou et al., 2024). In 2016 and early 2017 data, this appeared to refer to ‘voluntary’ returns implemented by the Police; but in the 2019-20 datasets is specified as ‘returns in the context of the returns directive [...] following a return order with a deadline for voluntary departure, holders of a 78α certificate (of non-removal for humanitarian reasons), withdrawal from an asylum claim’.

with informal and illegal policies, such as pushbacks, and rising racist sentiments cultivated to support such policies.

The first significant milestone in shaping return migration narratives was the economic crisis of the early 2010s. This period was marked by widespread unemployment, stagnant wages, and minimal social welfare provisions, which played a pivotal role in fostering discussions around return migration. Public discourses often scapegoated migrants, particularly undocumented ones, as contributors to the crisis. Migrants from Middle Eastern, Asian, and African countries who had settled in Greece since the mid-2000s were frequently labeled as ‘illegals’. These narratives were amplified by media actors, governing parties, and the rise of extreme right-wing and nationalist groups.

A striking example of such rhetoric occurred during the 2012 pre-election period when former Prime Minister A. Samaras stated, ‘Today Greece has become a centre for illegal immigrants. We must reclaim our cities, where the illegal trade of drugs, prostitution, and counterfeit goods are thriving’ (HRW, 2013: 15). These discourses also carried a strong spatial dimension, as undocumented migrants were associated with criminality and the degradation of Athens’ city center, frequently described as a ‘ghetto’ in political and official rhetoric (Koutrolikou, 2015).

The neo-Nazi organization Golden Dawn further contributed to the rise of nationalist and racist discourses. From 2008 onwards, Golden Dawn expanded its actions, beginning in Agios Panteleimonas—a central residential neighbourhood of Athens—and spreading racist violence across other parts of the city (Kandylis & Kavoulakos, 2011). The number of recorded incidents of racist violence surged dramatically, rising from an average of 7.75 incidents per month at the beginning of 2012 to 27.75 per month by the end of that year (Greek Ombudsman, 2013). These acts of violence were accompanied by racist narratives advocating for the expulsion of migrants to their countries of origin. Such incidents further intensified anti-immigrant sentiments and reinforced the narratives of return as a potential solution to the precarious existence faced by many migrants in Greece.

The years of the so-called ‘refugee crisis’ 2015–16 marked another critical milestone, particularly in its aftermath, which saw intensified pushbacks and significant incidents at the Evros border. The 2016 EU-Turkey Statement played a pivotal role in shaping return migration narratives during this period. While the initial months of the ‘long summer of migration’ in 2015 were characterized by the ‘refugees welcome’ movement, this sentiment quickly faded. It was replaced by restrictive, often emergency-driven responses to what was framed as a ‘refugee crisis’ in Europe. This shift influenced discourses, policies, and practices, leading to expanded border controls, increased returns, deterrence mechanisms, and a curtailment of asylum rights—both in Greece and across the EU. Governmental rhetoric further entrenched the above by categorizing migrants into two groups: those deemed ‘deserving’ of protection and asylum, and those labelled as ‘illegal’ and thus undeserving, who ought to be controlled, deterred, and potentially returned.

A turning point occurred at the Greek-Turkish border region of Evros/Edirne in February and March 2020. Greek authorities used tear gas, batons, stun grenades, rubber bullets, and live ammunition to repel migrants, violently pushing them back to Turkey. These events catalysed a securitization narrative, framing Greek borders as the EU’s first line of defence against migration and casting Greece as Europe’s ‘shield’ (Teunissen & Koutrolikou, 2022). Politicians leveraged these incidents to reinforce ‘Us-Them’ imaginaries, further polarizing public discourse. Notably, following these events, the implementation of returns under the EU-Turkey Statement, as well as the submission of asylum applications, was suspended. This action drew significant criticism directed at Greece. This also resulted in severe violations of

human rights (e.g. detention at warship Rhodes in Lesvos) and an obscure framework regarding the return of those not allowed to apply for asylum.

The subsequent intensification of pushbacks has been a central element in the evolving discourse. The mid-2023 shipwreck off Pylos that caused hundreds of casualties exemplified the devastating consequences of contested naval operations of the Greek Coastguard. These practices, aimed at preventing border crossings and reducing asylum claims, have transformed Greece's borders —hailed as 'Europe's Shield'— into grim symbols of Europe's mass graveyards.

4. Findings

This section presents the findings of the primary research, including interviews conducted in Greece, and is organized as follows: First, it examines migrants' agency in their movements and the reasons behind them. This includes not only migration to Greece *per se* but also the complexity and non-linearity of their trajectories, such as multiple returns to their country of origin, re-migration, re-returns to Greece, and circular movements driven by various factors. Second, it investigates the integration context in Greece, focusing on issues related to economic and labour precarity, housing deprivation, processes of irregularisation, institutional racism, policing, deportations and deportability, and the barriers to accessing essential services. The third section analyses social networks, family and institutions by focusing on the neighbourhood level (though not exclusively), in order to shed light on the development of social relationships in a wide spectrum between acceptance and racism, on the importance of friends and family and on migrants' involvement in migrant communities and other political organisations. Fourth, it discusses migrants' perceptions of returning to their country of origin, followed by their views on the possibility of migrating elsewhere. Finally, the chapter proposes a flexible typology of migration trajectories, grounded in the research findings and shaped by the prevailing social, political, and economic conditions in Greece.

4.1 Agency and movement

4.1.1 Reason for migration to Greece

This section explores the reasons behind movement towards Greece. The fieldwork revealed several interlinked factors that led to migration, related to security issues, economic hardships in the countries of origin, as well as prospects for reunification with family members already settled in Greece in the past.

Reza⁹, a 28-year-old Kurd from Iran, describes being forced to flee to escape persecution and torture by the Iranian regime after participating in the protests against the mandatory hijab that erupted in September 2022, following the assassination of Mahsa Amini.

'So, after I participated in this demonstration, the Iranian regime wanted to arrest me and put me in prison. So, I know they (would) torture and execute me. I don't know, (perhaps) hang me. Yeah, so that's why I left Iran. Because I am Kurd and I was born into a political family' (Reza, Kurd from Iran, 26/5/2024).

The pervasive fear and the general lack of safety caused by the chronic conflicts in Iraq led the 44-year-old Khalid, to the decision to escape and settle in Greece in 2000 when he was 19 years old. As he stresses:

'My country even now is not safe. There is always a war, whether it is small or large in scale. [...] I'm afraid because you're not safe, you're not sure that you're not going to face some stranger. In our country, the other person can get out of the car and take out a gun and kill you at that moment on the spot. We have been at war for so many years; it is easy to think that in almost every house there is a gun' (Khalid, from Iraq, 19/5/2024).

⁹As mentioned in Section 2, the names used in the Country Dossier are pseudonyms.

Most of the Georgian women who participated in the research are long-term settled migrants who decided to leave their home country due to the economic difficulties following the fall of the Soviet Union. Increased unemployment and poverty in Georgia were among the main factors for migration during the 1990s and early 2000s. Irina, a 64-year-old Georgian woman who arrived in Greece in 1997, recalls:

'I came to Greece in 1997 to find a job because the economic situation was very difficult in my country, there were no jobs anywhere, I was unemployed for four years' (Irina, from Georgia, 7/7/2024).

Elene, a 70-year-old migrant from Georgia, describes the poor living conditions, lack of electricity and inability to meet basic needs at that time. She points out that her desire to improve the lives of her children led her to migrate to Greece back in 2003:

'There was nothing and from zero it is very, very difficult to build something, to do something, to eat, to get dressed. And there was nothing. There was no electricity either. We had our electricity and gas cut off by Russia. [...] And then from there we started to get out of our country to build our lives and our families. I didn't want to send my children somewhere and I preferred to get out of the country myself and give something to my children, make their lives better' (Elene, from Georgia, 19/4/2024).

The burden of securing better living conditions for the remaining family members in home countries emerged as an important motivation for gendered migration in those years, as other scholars have argued (Vaious et al., 2007). Greece was a popular destination country for them, among other reasons, also due to the high demand for informal work in the domestic sector and in the field of elderly care services. Yet, several testimonies revealed their movement to be the result of a collective decision following a family consultation rather than a purely individual decision. For example, for Andrea, a 70-year-old from the Philippines, the decision to migrate was taken 35 years ago (1989) after a discussion with her husband, who at that time did not have a stable job, in order to secure better educational opportunities for her children. Similarly, Nino, a 58-year-old migrant from Georgia who settled in Greece in 2009, explains how deteriorating economic conditions in Georgia, combined with the burden of raising her daughter and her husband's loan payments, led to her decision to leave.

'I came to Greece for work because the economic situation in Georgia was very difficult and I had to find money to take care of my daughter and pay back a house loan that my husband had taken. [...] Things became more and more difficult financially after 1990, until then we had a good life, everything was fine, let's not hide, with the communist regime we had no financial problems, then there were no jobs, there was nothing' (Nino, from Georgia, 1/7/2024).

The economic difficulties in the country of origin were also highlighted as primary reasons for movement towards Greece by male Pakistani migrants. Employment precarity, low wages, extreme poverty conditions are significant factors in motivating decisions to migrate.³¹ 31-year-old Ali, from Pakistan, who settled in Greece in 2014, stresses how the inability to cover the cost of living in Pakistan led to his decision to leave.

'I was very young, I had heard that it was good, that you work here, that I'm going to make my life better. [...] There's a lot of problems afterwards working

there. Now it has become more difficult there. You can't work and pay the expenses of life' (Ali, from Pakistan, 15/4/2024).

Most interviewees of Pakistani origin reported that the decision to settle in Greece was invested with expectations of high job availability and better working conditions that would ensure better living conditions for them and their families. Ahmed, a 28-year-old migrant who arrived in Greece in 2018, outlines how employment difficulties in Pakistan and the burden of supporting relatives in his country of origin led him to the decision to leave:

'I had a problem there in Pakistan, not having a good job, if I had work I wouldn't have a good salary. [...] I am older than my brother and sister. I am sending money to them for survival. Because my mother and father, they're old now. They're not managing everything. But I'm coming for the whole family' (Ahmed, from Pakistan, 2/6/2024).

However, the economic situation in Pakistan is not the sole condition for fleeing. Economic hardships are intertwined with other social and family issues, as in the Zaid's case, a 24-year-old migrant who entered Greece in 2017 as an unaccompanied minor. In his testimony both the expectations with which migration is invested (in his case his studies) and the destabilization of Greece as country of destination are highlighted.

'I have many reasons. First of all, I fled because of my bad situation with my family. And second, I fled because of the financial situation (in Pakistan). [...] [...] Italy was like my final goal because Italy was very good for giving papers especially to Pakistanis. [...] My goal was to continue my studies. And then I came here. It was like an accident. [...] I was completely trapped (Zaid, from Pakistan, 31/7/2024).

Moreover, Zaid's example highlights Greece as a forced destination, rather than a destination of choice; in his case he ended up in Greece due to the smugglers' exploitation and non-compliance with their initial agreement. This may also be the case for other asylum seekers who started the migration journey with the aim of arriving to other EU countries but eventually were obliged to stay in Greece.

In addition, one of the interviewees mentioned that her movement towards Greece took place as a consequence of the previous settlement of relatives in Greece. Ana, a 25-year-old from Moldova, moved to Greece in 2007, six years later than her parents. As she narrates, her parents' legal status and the restrictions imposed on her mother by the conditions of live-in domestic work, delayed her reunification with her family.

'When I was eight years old, I left Moldova, but my parents had already left from there. I lived with my aunt, my mother's sister, in a village. [...] They (parents) couldn't (bring me from the beginning in Greece); my mom first of all was smuggled in. She was an illegal immigrant (in Greece). Then my dad joined her with papers and then they got jobs and then slowly they both got legal papers and they found a house because till then they were living... They were working in a house as a live-in. [...] When they rented a house, they brought me here' (Ana, from Moldova, 24/4/2024).

4.1.2 The role of networks in decision-making process

Personal social networks play a key role in both the decision to migrate and the choice of Greece as a destination country. Relatives, friends and compatriots, already settled, share their experiences and information about the Greek reality, job prospects and procedures for obtaining a residence permit. At the same time, they act as support networks, facilitating settlement and a smoother integration process in Greece, including connections with employers, housing opportunities, and language assistance. As Nino, from Georgia, identifies, pre-existing migration pathways play a key role in new migration routes.

'I came to Greece because my sister was already settled here. Wherever we have acquaintances, that's where we go' (Nino, from Georgia, 1/7/2024).

However, quite often information received before they migrate generates expectations that are dashed when they finally arrive in the destination country. Ali left Pakistan in 2014 with the intention of arriving in Germany following information from his compatriots. As he recalls, *'I had two or three people I knew from my village in Germany and they told me it was good money, they had jobs, and life was good'*. After achieving his goal and staying in Germany for a year and a half, he decided to move back to Greece, not only because he was informed that the asylum procedures there were stricter, but also because the cost of living was more expensive than he expected.

'But the difference is in life: over there you pay dearly. Here, okay, you don't have a lot of money from work, but you don't have a lot of expenses. I mean, over there I paid 5.50 euros for a souvlaki, donner, as they call it over there. Here it's 2.50 to 3 euros, for example, right? Life is very expensive over there, clothes and stuff like that' (Ali, from Pakistan, 15/4/2024).

Similarly, Omar, from Pakistan, cites that he decided to move from Turkey to Greece after being advised by his compatriots to come to Europe in order to enjoy better wages.

'I was told by my compatriots that I would not have any difficulties' (Omar, from Pakistan, 12/6/2024).

When he finally arrived in Greece in 2023, the situation he encountered was considerably different from what he expected, especially in terms of obtaining documents, concluding: *'2018 was easy here for asylum!'*. The challenges he faced, including precarious working conditions, led him very soon to enrol in the AVR program to return to Pakistan, currently waiting for the date of the flight.

Also worth noting is the existence of networks of smugglers and their connections with employment agencies in the destination country, which channel migrants into the labour market illegally, acting as the only source of information for migrants. Larisa, from Moldova, who settled in Greece in 1999, describes that her journey to Greece was entirely arranged by smugglers, including her connection with a recruitment agency in Athens:

'We had a phone number with us, for where we were going to take us to an office. We were paying a thousand dollars then to take us and give us information on where to go, not to leave us on the street. So he took us there. We had someone we knew waiting for us here. [...] It was an ordinary office in Omonia (square). They were Pontians that opened it, I think, they were from Armenia, and they had passports there, relatives here, it's like... I can't describe it. They could then open

offices, bring in women, girls to work. It was all illegal' (Larisa, from Moldova, 1/7/2024).

4.1.3 Multiple and complex trajectories

The fieldwork revealed that migrants' trajectories are characterised by a high degree of complexity rather than being linear, in the sense of a movement from a starting point to a destination point. A significant share of participants (12 out of 30) reported that they have returned to their countries of origin at least once, for a shorter or longer period of time, after their initial settlement in Greece for various reasons, including attempts to resettle permanently back home, visits to family networks, marriage, health issues or studies. The period of settlement in Greece, the socio-political situation in the country of origin and destination, as well as the legal status enjoyed by migrant populations in the destination country, tend to differentiate the possibilities of mobility and shape multiple trajectories of movement.

Some informants identified the financial crisis in Greece as a factor that multiplied the return trajectories, with the prospect of permanent resettlement in the countries of origin. Indicative is the testimony of the 22-year-old Elira from Albania, who was born in Greece after her parents and grandparents first migrated to Greece in 1998. She illustrates below the hardships that her family experienced during the financial crisis and the reasons that led them to return to Albania in 2008, when she was six years old, before they re-migrated back to Greece for a second time.

'That's important because we left during the crisis in 2008 that was one of the main criteria of us leaving Greece for a period. [...] A lot of the childcare was done by our grandmother, my mother's mother. And that played a big role. And by the time the crisis hits in 2008, and my grandparents are going back to Albania, this pushes my mother and my father who didn't see any way out in Greece with the financial part. My father was unemployed for a long period of time and my mother worked as a cashier in a supermarket. [...] There were times when even toast felt like a luxury. [...] So, we were living in extreme poverty. [...] and my parents wanted to invest in something else somewhere else, so they went back to Albania, they took us with them and we moved...' (Elira, from Albania, 17/10/2024).

The difficulties in running their own business in Albania, the pressure of family networks still residing in Greece, and other social constraints she faced there due to her queer identity, led her family to move back to Greece ten years later (in 2018). Return, however, may be different than what people imagined it would be – even if employment issues are resolved. Hussain for example, who settled in Greece in 2010, recalls cases of his friends and his brother from Pakistan, who, lacking legal documents, enrolled in the AVRR programme and returned to Pakistan with the prospect of permanent stay, due to the lack of employment or low-pay employment during the financial crisis. Below he articulates the reasons for their re-migration to Greece and the economic conditions that allowed it.

'Well, as soon as they arrived there (Pakistan), they were happy, cheerful, they spent about a year there, and then they got bored living there again. Because they had only learned to live differently. I mean, they were making money, working

here (Greece), having everything, and as soon as they returned permanently, they regretted it. It was a mistake. And then they came back again on foot, just like the others; they entered Greece again. [...] Not all of them. [...] I mean, finances played a role. The one who has money can return again; the one who doesn't have money, how can they return to Greece? The other two got married and stayed there. Those who had (money), well, I helped my brother, and my older brother did too. He returned again. The other one who came back, well, he had saved some money, and somehow he took out a loan and came back again' (Hussain, from Pakistan, 30/9/2024).

Eleven out of the 30 interviewees are long-term settled migrants who reported making sporadic returns of shorter or longer duration to visit their families and friends. For example, Elene, from Georgia, who settled in Greece in 2003 and has remained undocumented over this entire period, mentioned that she visited Georgia twice to see her family. Although she did not intend to settle there permanently, the difficulty of obtaining a visa again extended her stay in Georgia. Many male migrants, mostly of Pakistani origin, reported that these visits were made with the purpose of getting married and having a family in the country of origin, before moving back to Greece alone for work. For example, Hussain, from Pakistan, settled in Greece since 2010, stated that since he obtained his residence permit in 2018, he has visited Pakistan ten times, during one of which he got married. Significant numbers of testimonies highlighted the acquisition of a residence permit as a condition that multiplies return trajectories since it ensures re-entry into Greece. As cited by Tamer, who settled in Greece in 2006:

'Life doesn't stop at one point. Life goes on. I lived without papers, I made papers, then I had to think about my other life. I did my paperwork, went (to Egypt) and got married. I want to bring my family. [...] Now I'm legal, I can go and travel wherever I want' (Tamer, from Egypt, 19/5/2024).

The legal status and the different possibilities of re-entering Greece, related to the transnational agreements between countries, shape different possibilities of mobility and have a significant impact on the decision-making for movement. This is reflected in the narrative of Tamar, a 60-year-old woman from Georgia who settled in Greece in 2001. Since then, she has made two return journeys to Georgia. The first time *'freely'* when she had papers, and the second time under the AVRR program, 8 months before the interview while she was undocumented. Today she finds herself back in Greece with the right to stay for 3 months, after the Visa-free travel agreement between Georgia and EU, which came into force in March 2017 and allows Georgian citizens to enter EU with their passport and stay for no more than 90 days in any 180-day period. Her intention is to work informally for these months before returning to Georgia, then go back again, and so on and so forth. As she outlines, her plan is to continue these circular mobilities seasonally with the prospect of working.

'You think I have a future? [...] Now it's just this, to come (to Greece), work a little bit and go (to Georgia). [...] In three months, three and a half months, I can come back. Yes. To stay two and a half months and I'll go again. [...] As long as I can. Yes. When I can't (do it anymore), that's when I'll stop' (Tamar, from Georgia, 6/4/2024).

As Salome, from Georgia, mentioned when she also described the multiplicity and circularity of mobilities, a number of practices emerge in order for the Georgians to cross the borders without being arrested or denied entry, so that they continue working in Greece:

They (Georgians) do a lot of things. [...] To return (to Greece). [...] They change their names; they change their last name. They take their mother's last name, I don't know. [...] Yeah, they change, and they come back. Not directly from Georgia, from... Italy... I know, Romania... I know... They go somewhere and then here. This happens too! [...] Normally it's like that. Even if I hadn't been here that long and I wouldn't have gone with IOM anyway, with the passport, when you go out to Europe, you have three months. So, [...] one day before you have to go back to Georgia, you have to have a stamp. Then you cannot quickly go out again. You must stay 3 months in Georgia. It's a law". That's why they change the papers and the passport. They say that... I don't know, "I don't have any more or I want to change, I got married, I want to get my husband's last name or my wife's last name", something. They do that a lot. I've heard it too much" (Salome, from Georgia, 1/5/2024).

The practices described above emerge as critical within the context of migration. Many of these practices pertain to (temporary) re-migration to Greece, while others involve strategies employed by migrants to facilitate movement toward alternative destinations, especially to other European countries. For instance, Hussain, a Pakistani migrant, recounted that during his later years of residence in Greece, he managed to travel multiple times to Europe using the documents of a friend. These practices exemplify forms of agency exercised by migrants, albeit within a broader context of enforced immobility, shaped by the restrictive policies of the national asylum system.

The increase of pushbacks in the Greek borders during the last years also affects decisively migrants' trajectories and mobilities and indicates the forced and violent character of return practices, including human-rights violations and out-of-law practices imposed on them. Even if an in-depth examination of relevant issues extends well beyond the scope of this country dossier (for more details see Papatzani et al., forthcoming), the Box 1 below presents Ahmed's personal testimony of a pushback experience.

Box 1. Narrating a pushback experience

R: I would like, I remember from the other time that we talked, that you told me about your experience when you came to Greece. Let's go a bit back for a while. So you've told me that when you entered the Greek borders it was the army or I don't remember who pushed you back to Turkey. Is that right? Can you tell me a bit about this experience? Was it something they should do? What about this experience? Is this like now that they are doing these pushback things? Have you heard about push-backs in Greece? Also at the sea? Do you know that it happens in Greece? Yeah. A lot during the last years. And what about your own experience?

I: My own experience then, when I am coming here, I'm crossing the canal from the Turkey side; it's very easy. It's also not too dangerous. From Turkey in the night we crossed the border and also that night we were coming near the big road that goes to the national highway – the national highway that connects Turkey and Greece. From there the cars are going (with) too much speed like 200, 230 km/hour. When we were coming there, crossing the road, there were two cars very far away. We were (...) running the other way because we needed to cross the border and we needed to cross the road for two people to come and pick us up and take us to Thessaloniki. There were two cars coming very fast. We were on foot.

On foot. We were crossing the road. We were above the mountain and crossed the road. After we went down, the car came to pick us up. The one car, one car comes and goes. He sees us. Maybe he called the police. The other car was coming very fast and a person with us was hit by it. Because his arm hit the mirror, on the side when he ran. After that, we were crossing the border and maybe we were still near the car. The police were coming. They pick us up and take us to the police station, there are too many people. And that night that daytime they picked us up and in the night-time, they took us all in the van...

R: How many people and what kind of van? Was it a van of the police or with no letters?

I: That's a prison van, for prisoners. But inside, there are no sitting places, they put us inside by throwing us in. It was very difficult to sit there. We were not sitting, we were standing there inside. And they took us near the Turkish border through a canal and they also took a ship, a motorised ship, and they picked up a gun. The police picked up the gun. Two (others) stayed behind at the canal, and one was in the boat. They warned us, "if you are doing something "malakia" (bullshit) like that in the boat, I'll kill you". He also pointed the rifle at us. We were already afraid from the border crossing and it was too difficult, too much difficult. Because every country has many laws. And that is Greece. That is the first country in Europe when we enter. Because Turkey [...] is not considered as Europe for us, that is the door of Europe, that's how we think. That country, Greece, we think that it's a Euro door, Europe door. We think like that. But when we came here, our first experience was very bad because they are telling us if you come back again, we will kill you.

R: This is what they told you?

I: Yeah. In the canal, in the boat. They threw us, yeah, forcefully. They have a boat with a motor. There are two people in the boat. One is standing in the front and one is driving from behind. In the boat. They are police. Uniform. Yeah. They also have a jacket, a bulletproof jacket. And also have a gun. And they have on the scope a night mirror scopes. Before they make us cross, they check the border, if it was safe, if there was Turkish police, Turkish army nearby or not. First they check, then they throw us there.

R: You mean that they checked if there is anyone from the other side?

I: Yeah. So there was no one else on the Turkish side [...] They just put you in the boat and throw you there. [...] After that, we are going back because we are already tired after running for two days. We didn't have too much food, even our water was finished. So we went back to the Turkish side. And [...] they were searching every time. And the Turkish army was also coming every 10 or 5 minutes to check the border. We were going that was. And there are two vans coming. They already saw us, I think, because then the police threw us there [Turkish side], after, they are - take a fire, do one fire in the air, maybe that is a call to the Turkish policemen.

R: So they were two policemen, and how many immigrants?

I: Like 15.

R: [...] And you think that this is a sign for the other to come and check the boat?

I: Maybe for them or maybe for us. Don't come back. We are already afraid. After that the Turkish police took us. And also one thing I feel. The Turkish police treat us very well. Very well. Because then they receive us, after they take us to the detention center, give us food, everything, clothes, and also allow us to take a shower. But when the Greek police arrested us that day, they did not give us even one bottle of water. All day we were in the prison.

R: When they returned you to the other side, to Turkey with the boat, it was only, this happened once, only one time with the boat and the 15 people or they came back and took more people?

I: They took more, like that, like that, maybe 4 or 5 times, like 50 or more. It's a room like that in the prison in Greece, they take us there, they put us there, but there is not too much space, but people are too much even the toilet is shared for the prison and that is too much difficult to explain that situation. Even the people are sitting up, even I cannot do my leg like that, I did not have space. It was like 2018.

R: And then how long did you stay in Turkey?

I: One month I stayed there again and after I am coming back that way again, the same way. But that time we always if we want to sleep, two person are always checking around weather somebody's coming or not. And after that two sleeping the other two are doing that. With a group of people that we came together with. The second time I came, they took us... the police came to where we were, they put us in the car, the police came from behind us, but that person who's coming to receive us, he had a big car, a BMW, like that. But I sat behind the seat and I am always in the middle of the car. I'm not too afraid because it's very high speed, it's up to 200. The police are following us, they also know that inside that car, there is something illegal. Then the police came near us. He put the car the other way. There is no road. It's like a muddy road and police did not chase us because (...) the mud is coming from the tire; the police did not chase us because that's not like that carpet road it's a mud road' (Ahmed, from Pakistan, 2/6/2024).

4.2 Integration context, livelihood and socio-cultural context

This section examines the context of settlement and integration for migrants in Greece, with a particular focus on their livelihoods—encompassing employment and housing conditions—access to services, the socio-cultural environment, social relationships, issues of exclusion, and the impact of legal status on migrants' everyday lives.

A central characteristic of this context, as revealed through the interviews, is the recurring experiences of irregularity and unemployment faced by many migrants. For example, Farhan, an undocumented migrant from Pakistan currently enrolled in the International Organization for Migration (IOM) Assisted Voluntary Return and Reintegration (AVRR) program, and residing in OCAVRR, stressed that having legal documentation would enable him to access better employment opportunities, which might persuade him to remain in Greece. However, under his current circumstances, he stated that 'there is no other future, other than returning'. When asked whether he would consider returning to Greece in the future, he responded firmly, 'No more Greece' (Farhan, from Pakistan, 12/6/2024).

4.2.1 Economic situation

Economically, precarious working conditions are the norm for migrants in Greece. Labour precarity encompasses various dimensions, including job insecurity, low wages, and long working hours. It is often linked to the widespread prevalence of undeclared labour, particularly among migrants with irregular status. As Tamer, an Egyptian migrant, describes, working as an undocumented migrant has become so common that it is considered the 'norm'.

'Here in Greece they don't need papers. [...] it's better not to have it. [...] Everybody without papers works normally, they work illegally' (Tamer, from Egypt, 19/5/2024).

Moreover, employers explicitly prefer the informal and undeclared labour provided by irregular status, in order to reduce the working costs, as noted by Elene, a domestic worker for 20 years in Greece, currently retired in Georgia.

'No, most families said "I'm not going to pay you IKA". And some of them would ask "Do you want insurance?", "No, I don't have papers" I said, and they said, "Better! We won't pay for it!"' (Elene, from Georgia, 19/4/2024).

In cases of undeclared labour, migrants often face severe exploitation, including the lack of health insurance and retirement contributions, which results in limited access to healthcare services. They are also frequently denied agreed-upon wages.

To circumvent the vulnerabilities that derive from working without insurance or proper documentation, some migrants resort to irregular practices. These may involve bribing officials to obtain a false social security number (AMKA) and tax number (AFM) through networks that include personnel from state services. In other cases they may work by using another migrant's legal documents. For instance, an interviewee explained that he used his friend's documents for a year after his friend left for another country. He noted that his employer was aware the documents were not his own but had no issue with this arrangement.

Georgian women in Greece predominantly work as domestic housekeepers or caregivers, particularly for the elderly. Many secure these positions through specialized recruitment agencies based in Greece. As Tamar, from Georgia, describes, the agency she approached in central Athens found her a job within three days for a fee of 300 euros. According to several Georgian interviewees, they typically work throughout the week, with Sundays as their only day off. The homes where they are employed are often located in remote areas, far from central Athens.

Migrants who have been settled in Greece for decades often point to the economic crisis and austerity measures of the early 2010s as a period when they lost their jobs, faced prolonged unemployment, or experienced wage reductions. These circumstances made it difficult for many to afford the high costs of renewing their residence permits, jeopardising their legal status and potentially leading to irregularisation (Papatzani et al., 2024). In parallel, a significant number of established migrants left Greece or followed circular migration trajectories, as in the case of Khalid, an Iraqi migrant who has lived in Greece since 2000, but he was forced to leave the country in 2012 when his residence permit was not renewed.

Working conditions vary across different regions of Greece. Hussain, a Pakistani migrant settled in Greece since 2010, has held various jobs, primarily in Athens, often working more than 12-hour days in multiple positions to meet income and social benefit requirements. In recent years, he has worked seasonally on islands where the tourism industry is thriving. He notes that working conditions there are better than in Athens, citing higher wages and greater respect, due to the higher demand for labour on the islands, where employers struggle to find workers.

For migrants who have lived and worked in Greece for decades, particularly Albanians, pension issues have become a growing concern. Many have accumulated fewer work stamps than required, and although they may be eligible for retirement based on their working hours, they cannot apply yet because they need to demonstrate a minimum number of years of

employment to qualify for even the minimum pension. Recent legal changes further complicate matters, as they now stipulate a requirement of 40 years of regular, continuous residency, regardless of citizenship status. This effectively excludes nearly all migrants from accessing pension benefits, as many women from Georgia mentioned.

In late 2022, the two new legal measures regarding work-related residence permits aimed at addressing labour shortages attracted many rejected asylum seekers, particularly from nationalities with low recognition rates. For instance, Ali, from Pakistan, applied for a residence permit after his asylum seeker card expiration and is now employed in an Athens daily market, mentioning that currently the majority of migrant population has a job:

'Now that there are no land workers because most of them left for Italy and Spain to get papers, here they opened laws now with papers for this reason, because they had no land workers. Here at work (at the market) Athens and Attica had no land workers at all. [...] Now, all of us works, everyone works. [...] Now there's nobody staying at home, everybody's working, regular work' (Ali, from Pakistan, 15/4/2024).

Beyond work and income, precarious housing is a key dimension of economic insecurity, affecting not only migrants but also the Greek population. Asylum seekers awaiting decisions on their applications are currently entitled to accommodation exclusively in camps, following the termination of the urban ESTIA program. Conditions there are marked by significant challenges, including overcrowding, inadequate facilities, restricted freedom of movement, and stringent controls on daily life (Papatzani et al., 2022a). For others, particularly new arrivals without social connections, homelessness is common, especially in central Athens.

Rising rents and discrimination in the rental market pose significant challenges for migrants without access to housing provisions, making it difficult to secure rental agreements with homeowners. These challenges, compounded by the recent surge in living costs, often lead migrants—particularly undocumented individuals—to cohabit. This trend is especially common among single men, as highlighted in interviews with Pakistani migrants:

'But now, if one person is in the house [in Greece], it is very difficult to stay alone. In Greece with the bills and payments everything [...] we live together [...] if we have a roommate even for a brother, we don't have a difficulty because we share everything. And also we have «παρέα» (company)' (Ahmed, from Pakistan, 2/6/2024).

Established migrants often retain rented apartments even when not personally occupying them, but instead provide accommodation to newly arrived friends and relatives. This practice is also common among migrants who relocate for seasonal work or those who temporarily or regularly return to their home countries, particularly if they hold legal documents allowing them to visit family and later return to Greece.

For AVRR participants, housing precarity is addressed through their stay in OCAVRR, where they enjoy access to a number of services (for details, see Papatzani et al., forthcoming). Hassan, from Pakistan, who is unable to work due to health issues, has been accommodated in OCAVRR for two months and is waiting for the results of his medical tests so he can return. As he mentions, due to financial issues he has to stay in his room at OCAVRR all day: 'We have nothing (else) to do; we are here, without money'.

In this precarious context, many interviewees report that financial difficulties hinder their ability to support their families, despite viewing such support as an ‘obligation’, as Khalid, from Iraq, mentions. They specifically highlight the recent rise in living costs in Greece, which has significantly reduced the amounts they can remit compared to previous years. For others, supporting their families has been a long-standing practice, whether their relatives remain in their country of origin or live with them in Greece. For instance, Hussain, from Pakistan, has used his earnings to build a three-story house in Pakistan, where his wife and two children reside, and to purchase two additional apartments that are rented out to cover his family’s living expenses.

Andrea, a 70-year-old undocumented woman from the Philippines currently enrolled in the IOM AVRR program and residing at OCAVRR, shares her story of financial sacrifice. Over her 35 years working in Greece, she sent all her earnings to support her family, saving nothing for herself. After her five children became self-sufficient, she continued aiding her 17 grandchildren. Despite her extensive contributions, during the last three months of staying at OCAVRR she now relies on her children to send small sums of money. These are needed to cover her everyday needs (e.g., €220 via Western Union for occasional taxi travel and transportation to the hospital, typically on weekends) while waiting for her return flight.

4.2.2 Irregularisation and deportability

Legal status, particularly undocumented status, profoundly affects migrants’ integration opportunities, shaping their experiences, daily lives, and coping strategies. Irregularity is not merely the absence of legal status but a dynamic process of irregularisation involving shifts between regular and irregular statuses, affecting even those who were once ‘regular’ (Papatzani et al., 2024).

Since the 1990s, when Greece began receiving significant numbers of migrants, strict requirements for obtaining and renewing residence permits have been the norm. Even those who initially secured legal status often faced irregularisation due to challenges in meeting renewal conditions. High fees, the absence of continuous employment (even during the debt crisis of the 2010s), and other stringent requirements have created significant barriers to renewal, exacerbated by migrants’ precarious economic circumstances. As Alma from Albania notes for those who were trying to settle during the 1990s:

‘The first generation needs justice, not tolerance, not just understanding. [...] It is unthinkable after 20-30 years that people would lose their permit and they would lose it en masse. [...] because it was always extremely difficult to renew [...]. I was always under the threat of constantly losing my residence permit’ (Alma, from Albania, 14/3/2024).

Acquiring a residence permit remains a process marked by frequent renewals and long waiting periods until today, in a constantly changing legal framework. Losing the opportunity to issue or renew a permit not only hinders migrants’ ability to secure regular employment and better conditions, including health insurance, but also restricts their ability to travel back to their countries of origin. Many of the interviewees, including Georgian female migrants, remained for decades undocumented while working in Greece, as in the example of Elene, from Georgia, who worked for 20 years, undocumented, as a domestic worker in the country. Asylum procedures for applicants and beneficiaries of international protection have been also marked

by long waiting times, usually in dehumanizing conditions, and precarious reception conditions. As Reza, a Kurdish asylum seeker from Iran, stated, ‘The process of asylum is very, very hard... The waiting is very hard’. For migrants from ‘safe third countries’, asylum rejections directly impact their prospects, often resulting in irregular status.

For many, rejections and the inability to renew their status led them to consider leaving Greece, despite having established informal integration networks. The case of Mohammad, from Pakistan, who has lived in Greece for 13 years, illustrates this. A mistake made by his lawyer in his file jeopardized his residence permit application, leaving him in a state of uncertainty about the outcome. He describes this waiting period as follows:

‘And when I went to file the papers and I got this issue, for three or four months, it made me psychologically sick and I decided to leave Greece because I’m never going to get the papers. [...] To tell you the truth, sometimes I cried. I’m talking to you honestly because, I say, I’ve been abroad for so many years. [...] And I’m 13 years in Greece and I’m still zero’ (Mohammad, from Pakistan, 29/9/2024).

The effort to acquire residence permits also extends to migrants’ family members. Several preconditions, notably financial criteria based on migrants’ annual income, apply. Long waiting times and demanding requirements often push migrants to resort to irregular movements to reunite with their families, as described by Tamer, from Egypt.

‘I went to Egypt and got married. [...] I wanted to do the paperwork to bring my family. [...] I did it. [...] Eight months and still no answer. [...] After 8 months, life doesn’t stop where it left off 8 months ago. My wife got pregnant. My wife gave birth. You have to start the procedure all over again because now you have a child. [...] We did all this to bring the woman in legally. [...] I waited one, two, three months, in the end, no (rejection). [...] The answer was no. [...] But I didn’t marry a woman to leave her there. I sent her to Albania for vacation and I entered Albania and walked her out, with the help of a contact. [...] The country is forcing me to do the wrong thing’ (Tamer, from Egypt, 19/5/2024).

The overall exclusionary policies described above reflect what has been termed ‘institutional racism’, especially when migration policies are examined over time (Kandylis, Papatzani, and Polyzou, 2024). While conditions related to economic precarity, legal status, and irregularisation vary (based on the socio-political and economic context, as well as migrants’ years of settlement, networks, and labour market integration), exclusion persists for the majority. Despite recent invocations in the Press of ‘integration success stories’ for certain groups, such as Albanians, who have self-integrated in the absence of an official framework, the reality is one of deep institutional racism and exclusion, as argued by Alma, from Albania:

‘It is only a success story because we (they) declare it. [...] The Minister says we have a success story with the integration of Albanian immigrants and they applaud. [...] The mistake with the success story is that I don’t feel successful, I have Greek degrees and all that, but I have such institutional and social exclusion, which really makes you sick. The success story is not (about) what effort I make as an immigrant to fit in. I fully have the desire. I am more Greek than a Greek citizen, not Greek in the sense of national origin. I’m more local that way [...] But the success story is not just me trying, well how does it matter that I tried? When

I keep hitting a wall and you won't let me breathe, what success story... [...] Ask me what I've been through these 25 years and what exclusion the immigrant woman and the refugee woman gets. [...] So what success story really, [...] the only success story of the Albanians is the fight for their survival. What success story are you talking about? (Alma, from Albania, 14/3/2024).

Irregularisation and institutional exclusion are also reinforced by police practices that produce deportability in everyday life. Police 'sweep operations' in Greece, including those during the 1990s and the 2010s infamous 'Xenios Zeus', have a long history, with reports of rights violations and abuse during such controls (Pavlou, 2009; Karamanidou, 2016). Being irregular in Greece significantly shapes migrants' experiences, particularly in urban centers like Athens, where daily interactions between the police and migrants, or the threat of such interactions generate feelings of fear and insecurity.

'The first time I got caught, I fell down out of fear. I mean, I passed out, I don't remember anything. And when I opened my eyes, a Georgian woman hits me like this, "Wake up!" she said, "You're all right, they're gone, don't be nervous, everything's fine!"', because I was so scared' (Salome, from Georgia, 1/5/2024).

The fear of police practices is a widespread concern, particularly among undocumented migrants in Greece. As a result, they often avoid moving freely in the city, walking alone, forming social networks, or appropriating public space. Instead, they tend to live in precarious conditions, remaining in the city's shadows, or to alter the way they navigate in the city and appropriate urban space, as also shown in previous research (Papatzani, 2021). As Ahmed, from Pakistan, mentions: 'I'm not coming outside from my house. I'm just staying home'. Encounters with the police are a constant concern, even for migrants who have not personally experienced them. For Tamer, from Egypt, who has lived undocumented in Greece since 2006, he attributes his ability to avoid police attention to his character and knowledge of Greek, as he explains: 'I succeeded for 8 years without the police stopping me' (Tamer, from Egypt, 19/5/2024). Such examples reveal practices of agency to cope with everyday life needs in a hostile context characterized by the continuous threat of arrest.

In cases where multiple identities intersect, beyond that of ethnicity, such as gendered and political ones, the fear of arrest and deportation becomes 'something people have to watch out for', as Elira, a queer migrant from Albania describes. As she notes '*You feel like you're constantly in a regime [...] You are under constant surveillance*' (Elira, from Albania, 17/10/2024).

Police checks on the streets can result in migrants being taken to a police station for document verification. If found undocumented, they may be detained for indefinite periods in police stations or detention centers across the country, as illustrated by the experience of Ahmed. Arriving in Greece from Pakistan in 2018 and having applied for asylum, he was arrested a week before his interview after leaving his job as a gardener in Marousi. During a document check by the police, it was discovered that the papers provided by his lawyer were fake. He was held in Skala Oropou police station for four months, stating, 'four months I have not seen the sunrise. Always inside', before being transferred to Amygdaleza detention center in Attika, and then to another facility in Xanthi in northern Greece, where he spent a total of nine months in detention. As another interviewee notes, for those in detention, being transferred to a detention center is often seen as preferable, 'because the time spent in the police station does not count as time spent in the country' (Ali, from Pakistan, 15/4/2024).

While in detention, Ahmed observed that ‘those who apply for asylum [on the part of the detainees] are still there. Those who say “I want to go back, you deport me”, they are going out of the prison very soon’ (Ahmed, from Pakistan, 2/6/2024).

For some migrants, irregularisation, arrest, and detention are recurring experiences. For example, Ali, from Pakistan, was apprehended by the police twice after his residence permit and asylum status expired. The first time, he was detained for one and a half months, initially in a police station and then in a detention center. The second time, he was held for nearly seven months in a police station, and received a return order, after which he remained irregular in Greece for three years. During this period, he made efforts to establish and prove his presence in the country for at least three years, which eventually allowed him to apply for a residence permit as defined in the recent law.

The sequence of police checks, arrest, and detention is also a possibility for migrants registered in the AVRR program, including those residing in OCAVRR. Although they typically use their AVRR registration card to confirm their status, this does not guarantee that they will not be detained, as we have discussed elsewhere (Papatzani et al., forthcoming).

The sequence of police checks, arrest, and detention may be followed by forced removal operations, common since the 1990s, especially for migrants from the Balkans, notably Albania. As Karim, from Afghanistan describes, the current form of pushbacks was a common method of forced return a decade ago, and he recalls several examples of such practices:

‘Okay, you don't have papers, [...] they caught him, they put him in jail, in Amygdaleza, (then from) Amygdaleza (to) Northern Greece and Turkey. [...] Through the police, back, by force. [...] By road. Something that in recent years has been very well known. [...] but cases like that have happened two or three times, four times in total. [...] For the Afghans. [...] it was the 2000-2010 decade’ (Karim, from Afghanistan, 9/4/2024).

Moreover, our research revealed Ahmed’s (from Pakistan) personal testimony of an experience of a pushback, presented in section 4.1., Box 1. Testimonies also reveal more recent incidents of forced removal, even involving individuals who have applied for residence permits or asylum seekers while in detention. This raises concerns about the actual alignment of police practices with the law.

‘So, the father’s brother was detained. He was arrested by the police, and he was detained. [...] He even applied for a 7-year permit. [...] he applied for a seven-year permit, and he was waiting for the card, but still they forcefully detained him and deported him to Pakistan. [...] A year and a half ago. [...] He was there for almost two months in a closed camp in Korinthos. And then they deported him with closed eyes. They opened his eyes in Pakistan, and he saw that he was in Islamabad’ (Zaid, from Pakistan, 31/7/2024).

Collectively, all the above demonstrate how processes of irregularisation and deportability manifest across multiple intersecting scales, ranging from the local to the transnational. These dynamics emerge as critical issues in the daily experiences of migrants.

4.2.3 Access to services

Precarious working conditions, undeclared labour, low wages, and irregular status all contribute to restricted access to essential services like healthcare and education, since they affect migrants' ability to pay for residence renewal fees. As Ismael illustrates, this connection between economic hardship, legal status, and access to services is clear:

'For years I was employed in farms (olive trees, etc.), earning approximately 25 euros per day, in bad working and living conditions. These hard conditions have worsened my asthma and since I have no legal documents I have no access to hospital, medicines, etc. No documents, no work, no insurance, no AMKA, no hospital. [...] With no documents I have no access to health insurance, hospitals and medicines' (Ismael, from Burundi, 12/6/2024).

Access to public healthcare services has been increasingly restricted in recent years through legislation and institutional procedures, particularly for the undocumented, who are only eligible for emergency treatment. In many cases, migrants rely on the discretion and dignity of public healthcare personnel to receive the care they need. Those who can afford it turn to the private sector, as mentioned by several interviewees.

Obstacles to equal access to education were also highlighted. Navigating public services and bureaucracy was another challenge, particularly for migrants' children. This issue is compounded by the fact that these children often cannot rely on their parents for guidance, as the parents may lack the knowledge or resources to assist them in navigating these systems.

'And I had to learn from scratch, because I [...] had no idea in general how the public system works, like welfare, bureaucracy, health care and all that. And that's a huge issue because our parents [...] due to the lack of documentation they don't have access to public services, so they don't have the motivation or the opportunity or a reason to see how to navigate public services' (Elira, from Albania, 17/10/2024).

In addition to health and education, access to legal assistance is a critical issue, especially for those seeking to appeal asylum decisions or renew their residence permits. Migrants and refugees often pay large sums to lawyers for help with regulating their legal status. Recently, incidents of exploitation have been reported, where migrants were provided with false legal services and documents by individuals claiming to be lawyers or by actual lawyers who charged excessive fees despite the minimal cost of the service.

4.3 Social networks, family and institutions

Migrants cultivate diverse social networks alongside their mobility and settlement practices, which play a vital role in sustaining their livelihoods and fostering sociability. These networks often provide a foundation for informal integration trends to develop, countering the restrictive integration environment and limited opportunities previously discussed.

Such networks emerge across various scales and domains of everyday life: within local neighbourhoods, during migration journeys, in camps while awaiting asylum decisions, at workplaces, or in urban meeting spaces. These relationships are formed both within ethnic groups—among migrants from the same country of origin or those encountered during

migration—and inter-ethnically, involving Greeks and others in shared living or working environments. Together, these connections facilitate essential support and adaptability in navigating daily life within a new social and cultural context.

4.3.1 Neighbourhood and beyond: between mutual care and racism

Local relationships and networks within neighbourhoods play a pivotal role in shaping the everyday lives of migrants and refugees in Greece. In urban centers like Athens, such interactions arise across various neighbourhood spaces, including the micro-scale settings of apartment blocks, streets near their homes, public spaces like parks and squares, and local shops or businesses that serve as meeting points for diverse groups of residents. These connections often extend beyond residential areas. For instance, migrant women working as domestic workers may form relationships in the neighbourhoods where they reside or at their employers' homes, which are often located far from city centers or in other parts of the country. Reflecting on these experiences, Elene, who returned to Georgia through the AVR program, recounts:

'Very, very good relationships (with Greeks) and now I still have contacts and from where I was working lately, in a village towards Megara. And from there I still have communication and not even a week has passed (after I returned to Georgia), and they call me and ask me, how are you, do you want something, do you want me to help you with something, send you something. When I was working there (in Greece), I had a very good relationship with my neighbours. [...] I miss them, all of them' (Elene, from Georgia, 19/4/2024).

Such relationships emerge in a mundane way but crucially determine migrants' experiences, ranging from simple acquaintances, sometimes with overtones of hidden prejudice, to relationships of care and mutual help. Usually, such relationships are also gendered, as the narratives of Georgian and Pakistani interviewees revealed about their local networks. In other cases, neighbourhood relationships transcend gender identities and are established on the basis of particular needs. For example, Ali, from Pakistan, who works in local street markets describes exchanges of mutual help and care on an everyday basis between himself and elderly people, especially women, in his neighbourhood.

'In the neighbourhood I have 2-3 acquaintances, 2-3 old ladies over there for whom I buy things from here (the street market – 'Laiki') and I carry them for their old man. I hang out with them a bit. Sometimes they send me some candy and look after me, because I live alone and I look after the house too. I leave the house at night and come home at night.... It's a good neighbourhood. They take care of me and I take care of it' (Ali, from Pakistan, 15/4/2024).

These relationships often lay the groundwork for what has been described as 'urban citizenship', transcending traditional notions of citizenship and integration tied solely to state-driven, formal provisions (Vaiou et al., 2007; Zavos, Koutrolikou, and Siatitsa, 2017). In many cases, such networks help mitigate the systemic obstacles migrants face within official integration frameworks. For instance, Larisa, from Moldova, who has lived in Greece since 1999, shared how her connection with a neighbourhood nurse facilitated access to a surgeon 'living at the corner'. This personal network enabled her to secure a discounted cancer

operation, an option she otherwise could not afford in the private healthcare system, which was her only option as she was excluded from public health care.

However, the same urban and neighbourhood spaces that foster these supportive networks can also serve as spaces where relationships of distance, discrimination, and even xenophobia and racism may manifest also in a mundane way (Papatzani, 2021). A place perceived as ‘home’ can simultaneously become a site where racism and prejudice are deeply felt:

‘Where I live now (centre of Athens) it’s like my home now, I grew up here. I do feel I belong here but they haven’t made me feel 100 percent you know. Because there are still these racist incidents. In the past, it used to be more, more Greeks who spoke badly like that’ (Ana, from Moldova, 24/4/2024).

Racism extends beyond the neighbourhood level, permeating various urban spaces tied to daily activities and movements. It can manifest in everyday contexts such as public transportation, workplaces, and other communal areas. Beyond institutional forms, as discussed in Section 4.2, racism frequently operates on an everyday level, shaping interactions and experiences in subtle yet pervasive ways. At times, it escalates into violent practices, as witnessed in Athens especially during the early 2010s (see Section 3.3), highlighting the multifaceted and persistent nature of racism in urban environments.

Although overt violent racist manifestations have diminished since the trial of the neo-Nazi Golden Dawn, everyday racism has all but disappeared. For instance, Tamer, an Egyptian migrant, experienced racism from other parents while his daughter played in a neighbourhood playground. Similarly, Hussain, from Pakistan, reported encountering systematic racism in his workplace, which has become a recurring challenge in his daily life and a motivating factor for considering migration to another European country, as discussed in Section 4.5.

Racism and discrimination also surface in diverse public and private spaces. Ana, from Moldova, recounted encountering racist hostility at a beach, where an elderly Greek woman yelled, ‘Go to your country, sit there, wherever you want’. Similarly, Elira, a queer migrant from Albania, shared their experience of transphobic attacks in Greece, highlighting a lack of trust in police protection, especially for queer migrants: ‘We don’t expect the police to protect us. Especially if we are immigrants and queer immigrants’.

Additionally, everyday racism is not limited to interactions with locals but can also occur among migrants. For instance, migrants from Pakistan have reported experiencing discriminatory behaviour from those who settled in Greece during earlier migration flows, such as in the 1990s, revealing another layer of exclusion between different migrant groups.

4.3.2 Friends and family situation

Relationships with friends and family play diverse roles in shaping migrants’ settlement, integration, and mobility experiences. Many interviewees described being separated from their families upon migrating to Greece. This was especially common among male migrants from Pakistan and female migrants from Georgia, some of whom left young children in the care of their parents to provide for them from abroad. As a result, family members often remain in the country of origin or are dispersed across various countries. For others, the presence of a family member already settled in Greece influenced their decision to migrate, offering vital support through information, guidance, initial shelter, and sometimes work opportunities. However,

in many cases, these relatives have since moved on from Greece, leaving migrants to take on the role of supporting other family members in their migration and settlement journeys.

Family relationships among migrants vary widely, shaped amidst different obligations, responsibilities, and individual circumstances. For many, the responsibility of financially supporting relatives remains a significant factor, while others pursue more individual trajectories for personal reasons. The desire to visit family, often delayed for years due to residency challenges, becomes a key goal for many, once they obtain residence permits.

When family members reside in Greece, relationships range from supportive to burdensome—sometimes simultaneously. For instance, Ahmed, from Pakistan, who arrived in 2018, shared that migrating elsewhere is not an option for him, as decisions must be made jointly with his cohabiting brother. Family involvement also extends to decisions about future movements or returns. Mohammad, from Pakistan, described migrating to Greece to join his father, who lived and worked there. However, as his father aged and faced health issues, the family collectively decided on his return to Pakistan. Following this, Mohammad assumed financial responsibility for supporting his father even after his return.

Friendship networks among migrants vary widely, spanning local neighbourhoods, cities, and even transregional or transnational connections. These relationships often form and thrive in diverse spaces of everyday life, including workplaces, public spaces, and leisure areas, as well as during daily navigation through the city. Many friendships stem from shared migration experiences, such as travelling together or spending time in camps. For instance, Zaid, from Pakistan, who lived in Elaionas camp near central Athens, maintained close relationships with people he met there even after leaving the camp. He reflected, *‘We are still like best friends. [...] they are from Afghanistan... from different countries’*.

Relationships with employers also play a significant role, particularly for women working as housekeepers and single male migrants from countries like Pakistan. These connections often provide more than just employment; they facilitate language learning in a context where adult language education is not publicly available.

However, the ability to maintain both friendships and family networks often depends on time constraints, especially for migrants working long hours in remote locations. Female domestic workers, for example, typically rely on their single day off—usually Sundays—to visit their social networks.

‘On Sundays when I have the day off, I visit my family (niece, cousins, etc.) residing in Faliro. My niece, who is married and has a 7-year-old child, lives in Faliro, works in house cleaning, “a lot of hard work”, and will return to Georgia later, when she can, “because now her child has started school here. We will see how our lives and our luck go” (Nino, from Georgia, 1/7/2024).

For migrants in Greece, family ties and shared nationality do not always lead to closer relationships. In some cases, migrants reported avoiding connections with co-ethnics or preferring friendships over familial relationships. As several migrants noted, personal preferences or past experiences sometimes shape these choices, leading them to prioritize friendships that offer more support or comfort than family connections.

‘In Greece I found Georgian ladies with whom I had a better relationship than with my relatives. Because we had gone through the same situations, the same problems. And so, I have a better relationship with them’ (Elene, from Georgia, 19/4/2024).

Thinking his overall experience and relationships in Greece since his first settlement in Athens in 2006, Tamer, from Egypt describes his family and friend networks as follows:

'I'm Egyptian, I live in Greece. I don't have any friends from Egypt now. All my friends are Greek. [...] My life is here. We go out, we go to the beach, we work, we do our insurance stamps, we go out with friends. [...] (his young daughter) has a friend, she has company, she goes to her friend's house, the friend will come to us. So I have people here in Greece, I don't have people in my country. I mean, in my country now I have my brothers and sisters and my mother. We talk on the phone and that's enough, we are happy. [...] Here, we talk every day. Texting, talking, going out. I might go on a job and leave my kids and my wife alone. "Knock on wood" if something happens to the kid I have a hundred women here, a hundred girls, a hundred guy friends, to tell them that I need this thing done. If I have no money, I call a friend of mine and tell them my money is running short until the end of the month. I want 500 euros now to roll for this month [...]. I've got everything here. I can live with a job, without a job, with a lot. Because I got... let's say now we're thinking about having a house, of my own. I have two kids here, I'm raising them. This is happening now. Tomorrow, the day after tomorrow, he's going to the army' (Tamer, from Egypt, 19/5/2024).

Overall, the impact of relationships with friends and family on migrants' trajectories is multifaceted. On one hand, such relationships can facilitate integration and mobility across various levels, including the transnational level, particularly in cases where families are geographically dispersed. Conversely, the persistence of family networks may pose challenges for some individuals, who instead rely predominantly on friendships and co-ethnic or inter-ethnic networks established in Greece. Shared experiences, localities, and the duration of settlement significantly influence the manner in which these relationships affect migrants' social interactions, experiences, and overall trajectories.

4.3.3 Involvement in migrant organisations

Migrant organisations and communities in Greece play a crucial role in maintaining networks among co-ethnics and providing essential support for everyday needs, livelihoods, education, and social connections. Migrants often turn to these communities for assistance tailored to their specific needs and the unique characteristics of each group. For example, the Athens Georgian House runs a Sunday school where mainly families with young children attend classes to learn the Georgian language. Additionally, in Athens, there are also few other schools for migrants, including the Open School for Migrants in Piraeus, where some interviewees attended Greek language courses, and the Sunday School for Migrants.

'(The school) has helped me very much. I am doing lessons and my wife is also doing lessons. Even [his daughter], here if you bring your children, people ask her 'what do you want, to paint, to look at a book?' Here people have a soul' (Tamer, from Egypt, 19/5/2024).

Other migrant and refugee communities, such as the Afghan Community in Athens, not only provide educational and recreational activities but also offer assistance and advice on legal

procedures, including asylum applications and related rights. In some cases, migrant communities and organisations focus on labour rights, such as the Pakistani community, which primarily addresses issues related to labour conditions, racism, and discrimination. Similarly, the ‘Albanian Immigrants and Solidarity Initiative’, established in 2018, engages in political activism, including among others advocating for migrants’ pension rights by challenging recent laws that limit their access to the minimum pension.

‘As with pensions. We have made a campaign and we are collecting signatures and handwritten signatures; to abolish the Katrougalos (law) and to be on equal terms with the locals when it comes to the pension rights, and to make a transnational agreement with Albania, so that the Albanian state contribute in this, because people have worked there as well’ (Alma, from Albania, 14/3/2024).

For others, political participation is essential, particularly through mobilisation and activism focused on combating racism, xenophobia, and discrimination against migrants. Many political migrant organisations also address issues of antifascism and antinationalism, which are central to their daily activities and agendas. As the representative of the Albanian Immigrants and Solidarity Initiative noted:

‘So the initiative started by some of us of the first generation who have been politically involved for 25 years. [...] The subject of the action would be immigration and all the problems, racism and all that, and all the problems that are of concern to society at large. And the refugee issue and the racism that other social groups have in an anti-fascist, anti-racist and anti-nationalist context, but it will also have as its objective the confrontation of nationalism. [...] So nationalism both here and there, which should begin to sensitise both societies, Greece and Albania’ (Alma, from Albania, 14/3/2024).

In other cases, antiracism intersects with broader social issues, such as feminism and LGBTQI+ rights, prompting migrants to seek collectives that adopt an intersectional and progressive approach in their advocacy.

‘Initially, I went to the place that was more accessible, which was the feminist collectives. [...] But then somehow I had gotten closer to more communist spaces, from an intersectional point of view always, that put in the queer part and the women's issue and the anti-racist and anti-fascist, everything in general. [...] And at the same time, I went to the Albanian Immigrant Initiative for the first time a few weeks ago, [...]. And in general, I've been to a lot of queer collectives and queer assemblies. [...] I know that there are some queer Albanian political spaces (in Greece) [...] it exists as a space of safety and solidarity for those people who had the intersectionality of Albanian and queer identity together, which is something that is not talked about enough’ (Elira, from Albania, 17/10/2024).

4.4 Perceptions about return

4.4.1 The complex factors shaping return perceptions and decisions

Perceptions about further movement to countries of origin are shaped by multifaceted factors that include economic, social, and socio-political conditions in the countries of origin, as well as migration policies and the socio-political situation in Greece.

Political and security issues were stressed by some interviewees as significant obstacles. Karim, from Afghanistan, highlights that the repression and the human rights violations imposed by the Taliban rule, preclude any thought of returning to Afghanistan. His narrative depicts the deprivation of rights and freedom for women, marginalisation of ethnic groups, arbitrary arrests, torture, and killings.

‘Women can’t go out on their own. Women can’t work. Women can’t travel. Women have no right to speak. [...] Recently, four people from one family were arrested. The son of the family disappeared, we don’t know where he is, his three sisters, they killed them. The Taliban went to their house because they are from another tribe, they were caught, they were taken to the detention center [...] That is, even rape, even mutilation, even killing, they do vile acts [...]. If you’re a man, they shoot you on the spot [...]. And that’s why those who are in Europe or in Greece don’t want to go back’ (Karim, from Afghanistan, 9/4/2024).

Elira, from Albania, points out other social issues that prevent return routes. As an openly queer person she doesn’t feel ready to expose herself to the Albanian community, emphasising that this was a decisive factor in her desire to leave. The normalisation of violence, the frequent attacks against the queer community, the lack of an institutional framework for protection, as well as the fact that many queer people are forced to hide their identity, constitute for her discouraging living conditions in Albania.

‘I had in mind that I don’t want to hide my own identity and I’m not going to be somehow restricted by any boundaries [...] recognising that there is a risk to my physical integrity in Albania that is largely preventing me from going back. [...] Because violence against queer people in Albania is very much normalized and you won’t find a way out [...] There will be harassment from state institutions as well, there is no legal framework that will protect you from anything, the LGBTQ community for the system is non-existent’ (Elira, from Albania, 17/10/2024).

Moreover, the adverse economic conditions prevailing in home countries emerge as a significant deterrent to return. For young Pakistani men who hold or are in the process of obtaining a residence permit, the main constraints for return are the lack of job opportunities, the low wages and the exhausting working hours. As Hussain, from Pakistan, states *‘It’s a different life there. I can’t work like that there; I can’t stay. And I can’t earn that kind of money’*. In many testimonies the economic obstacles are intertwined with other social aspects of migration. Ali, from Pakistan, points out that the different mentality acquired after his long stay in Europe, combined with the disruption of social relations in his country of origin, reinforce his decision to stay in Greece.

‘I will not go there because now everyone there will have forgotten me. In the neighbourhood they won’t know me anymore. And if I go there, it’s very difficult to stay there. Because now within my mind there is a very big difference... [...]

Those who are abroad (compared to) those who are there (Pakistan) have a big difference in their mind' (Ali, from Pakistan, 15/4/2024).

Additionally, many migrants referred to the money invested in their migration to Greece, which in many cases involved loans –or debts to smugglers' networks– that were supposed to be repaid through work in the destination country. This fact, combined with the difficulty of crossing borders, is a deterrent to considering returning frivolously. Below, Ahmed, from Pakistan, elaborates his opinion on forced returns, also underscoring the sense of personal failure and the breach of the commitment of financial support to the family that is inherent in any return action.

'I think without people's permission, forcefully (return) is not good. Because we are coming through very difficult routes. [...] Because first of all, they invest, they give the money to the people to cross the border. That money may have been taken from a friend or brother like that, like borrow. [...] After all that (forced return), he is losing everything. Maybe his brother and sister if you don't have one, they also leave you because you lost your job, you lost your time. Even if you borrow money and also you need to pay back' (Ahmed, from Pakistan, 2/6/2024).

Despite these challenges, certain conditions in the country of origin could lead to return for Pakistanis. The possibility of running a farming business on personal farm property or, for older people, the prospect of shifting the burden of the family's financial support to children who have now grown up either in Pakistan or in Greece may constitute incentives for making the journey back. In some cases, the decision for return is a family matter and is taken by younger family members for their parents. For example, Mohammad, from Pakistan, who settled in Greece in 2011, enrolled his father in the AVRR program in 2013, and as discussed below he enumerates multiple reasons that led him to this decision.

A decision factor in his father's return were the security concerns in Greece, due to the rise of Golden Dawn. Similar socio-political issues and migration policies in Greece emerge as important factors in the decision-making processes. Difficulties in obtaining residence permit, the protracted irregular status and the resulting exclusion from the labour market and health care provisions, or the precarious undocumented working conditions which hinders the support to families in home countries play a crucial role in the decision to return. Two undocumented migrants from Pakistan, who have already initiated return under the AVRR program, claimed that if they had documents, they would not have taken this decision. More specifically, Farhan, from Pakistan, stated, *'If I had papers, I would stay in Greece. I am tired here [...] Now there is no other future, other than returning!'* Similarly, Omar, from Pakistan, who arrived in Greece in 2023, highlights that the intensification of police checks in Greece and the fear of possible detention led him to the decision to return to Pakistan. As he explains, *'If you get arrested here and stay at the police station, what happens? What will happen back with my family? [...] if they gave me documents here, I would cancel my return NOW! [...] If you're having a hard time living here and you're drowning, you'd better go home!'*

In addition, the financial difficulties in Greece may lead to a reconsideration of the available options. This is the case for Salome, a 44-year-old woman from Georgia, who decided to enrol in the AVRR program due to, among other reasons, the overall increasing cost-of-living she is experiencing in Greece and the inability to meet basic needs for her and her daughter. Although she is aware of the difficulties she will face there, she is optimistic about returning home.

'The years go by. Nothing changes. It gets a little bit worse [...] It's hard living here now, everything is expensive, but the salary hasn't gone up. [...] Now life there (in Georgia) is expensive too [...] I mean it comes out the same to me, you live just to get food. [...] The difference is that you're in your home country. You are close to your family. And here you are alone. [...] I return with hopes!' (Salome, from Georgia, 1/5/2024).

For long-term settled women, from Georgia and Moldova, who were mostly middle-aged upon their first settlement in Greece, the thought of returning is associated with feelings of nostalgia and their families living back home. Nino, a 58-year-old woman who came to Greece in 2009, shares her impatience to return to Georgia and see her relatives after so many years.

'I'm happy with my current employer, but my problem is that I'm away from my family. This is the main reason I want to return to my country [...] Who doesn't want to come back to be with their family, who doesn't want life with their own people? So many years I see my family only from the computer' (Nino, from Georgia, 1/7/2024).

Furthermore, the choice or the thought of returning also comes as a consequence of the limited work options and reduced strength due to age. As Larisa, a 70-year-old woman from Moldova who has been in Greece since 1997, says

'Now we are old, we can't do it anymore. So when you have no strength, you go back. [...] I'm tired, I say, I don't want anything else at all. That's because I don't have much time' (Larisa, from Moldova, 1/7/2024).

This is combined with the physical exhaustion caused by the working hardships and often the labour exploitation they faced for many years, mainly in the domestic sector in Greece. The 64-year-old Irina, from Georgia, who settled in Greece in 1997 and has been working for several years in the care of elderly people, describes her plan to return to Georgia as soon as she meets her goal.

'Now I am waiting to fill in a few missing stamps in order to receive an early pension and return to my country, because I can no longer work. [...] In addition, I am forced to do it because I have health problems with my back and I cannot work with elderly people, often bedridden, I can only hang out with them, now I have a back problem, so many years bent over them' (Irina, from Georgia, 7/7/2024).

Health issues, and the disqualification from work that they entail, emerged as a crucial - and in some cases sole - factor that prompted some interviewees to enrol in AVR. The restricted access to health care provisions in Greece also contributes to their decision. For example, Arjun, from India, mentioned that if he did not have health issues preventing him from work, he would not have considered returning to India, since he still owes money to the smugglers and receives threats. For Usman, from Pakistan, a holder of a residence permit in Greece, the decision to return was taken due to a serious medical problem with his leg. After 2.5 months of staying at OCAVR, receiving treatment and improving the condition of his leg in order to receive the 'fit-to-travel' confirmation, he stressed that he regrets it, and he is in the process of disengaging from the program. When asked about the reason for his withdrawal, he comments, *'My leg is better. My boss wants me, he doesn't want me to leave! [...] I have lived in Greece*

all my life, what should I do in Pakistan? Another reason that prevents him from proceeding is that his return with IOM would prohibit any re-entry to Greece for the next five years.

4.4.2 Perceptions and experiences of AVRR in Greece

The AVRR program which grants return tickets, financial aid upon departure, as well as in-kind assistance for those eligible for reintegration in home countries, seems to be an attractive option for some migrants, but only provided they have already made the decision to return. A variety of perceptions emerge among individuals enrolled in or considering participation in the AVRR program, accompanied by diverse experiences reported by those who have already returned through the program or witnessed the return of their relatives.

First, for those who choose to return through AVRR, enrolment presupposes that the applicants withdraw their asylum applications, and refrain from any rights coming with a real or potential regular status – either of an international protection beneficiary or a migrant with a valid stay permit or even the temporary ‘regularity’ of an asylum seeker. This process can be seen as a peculiar (self-)irregularisation, i.e. of accepting an irregular status, in order to take advantage of the benefits of AVRR. On the other hand, Arjun, from India, has never had legal documents and obtained any documents for the first time when he registered for the AVRR program. Thus, as we have argued elsewhere, irregularisation as a process constitutes an important part of the AVRR’s implementation. Irregularity may be seen as an important pre-condition for the implementation and maintenance of AVRR, or in other words, AVRR seems to ‘regularize’ irregularisation (Papatzani et al., forthcoming).

Moreover, experiences of AVRR participants include different types of encounters with the authorities, as part of the AVRR procedure. Salome, from Georgia, is a former asylum seeker settled in Greece since 2016 who returned to Georgia on 8/5/2024. She narrates her experience of refraining from her asylum claim to be enrolled in AVRR program and the procedure that followed until her departure.

I said it’s over, it’s done, the cancellation (of the asylum claim) has been made, and okay the IOM said, “You have to make an appointment now with Allodapon (Aliens Department of Greek Police) for fingerprints” and that stressed me. When we went there, we were 10 women together... [...] Georgians. [...] In Petrou Ralli. [...] So, I went upstairs, it’s one room which is like... when the cops catch you and put you behind the... Like that, like (cell)... [...] And we’re joking, the Georgians, we said “Look at this, it’s like we’re gangsters!” They really put us in there, they put us in (bars) [...] Yeah, okay they didn’t close the door. But you must not go outside, no cell phone, no water, no nothing. [...] They kept us for about three hours. We’ve been waiting (for fingerprinting) ... [...] You can see back here above (shows on a photo in her phone) how many (women) there are! And there are elderly women [...] They took our fingerprints, and we said okay now they’re going to give us our passport to go back and they will tell us when to come for the papers that the police are going to give us. [...] And then they said, “No, we have to take pictures!” What pictures? And believe me, it’s the worst shock I’ve ever been through. [...] This way, that way (shows the ways the police took photos of them), then you go near the wall, which says how tall you are, and they measured it from there, they took pictures there too. “Sit like this!”, they said “Front!”, “Head up!”, “Head like this!” and he shouts, the person who takes the pictures. He shouted very badly at the woman who was an old woman. It was difficult for her

to get up and sit there on the stool. “You didn’t sit like that, what is this!”, and other things like that. And my daughter who doesn’t speak Greek, he said something to her, and I told him “She doesn’t speak Greek”. “I’ll go out and explain to her!” I said. “Sit down, don’t come out, sit there, as I told you” he said. “What are you shouting about? Why are you shouting? It’s like we’ve killed someone. What’s that?” (I said). But then a girl I met (there) told me, “Shut your mouth! Shut up now, don’t do things like that, or they will really detain us! Stop it now! Be patient and let’s get out of here”.

[...]

Okay, that paper from Allodapon (Aliens Department of Greek Police) when you get it, you have to take it to IOM to get it stamped and do some things that they need there [...] Then they tell you “we’ll call you for the tickets” and I -who begged really hard- and I really needed the first one (plane), whatever that was, they called me on the 25th (of April)... I gave them a doctor’s note as well... Because with what happened with my son, I was anxious and my heart hurt. I said it was from anxiety and stuff, but they told me to check it again. I checked and I did a triplex and all that. I was given a doctor’s note that I return and that I can travel, that it’s okay. And then they told me “We’ll call you! We’ll call you to tell you about the tickets!”. April 25th was that, I went back to work and somehow in an hour and a half they called me and they said [...] “Your tickets have been issued” he said, “You’ll come on May 7th to get them in hand from here!” [...] So, we will all go together to the airport and as I’ve heard there must be a Georgian woman there who will travel with us to Tbilisi. [...] Yes, to make sure that we are all together and that we will all go to Georgia together. [...] It’s like they check that you actually go to your country. And they keep an eye on you on the plane in case you have high pressure and stuff like that. And for those who don’t speak as well. There are Georgians who have lived here for 20-30 years but they don’t speak Greek. They don’t understand. “Hello!” (in Greek) is all they can say’ (Salome, from Georgia, 1/5/2024).

Perceptions and experiences of AVRR also revealed migrants’ dissatisfaction on different aspects of the procedure. For example, some interviewees commented that the amount of money given upon departure (1000 for those residing in mainland and 500 euros for those residing on the islands) is negligible compared to the money they have spent to move towards Greece. Tamar, who returned to Georgia with the IOM, eight months ago and came back to Greece, states:

‘They give us 1000 euros and send us home. I left. [...] This money is nothing. Absolutely nothing’ (Tamar, from Georgia, 6/4/2024).

Most of the interviewees enrolled in AVRR mentioned that they have also applied to receive in-kind reintegration assistance for various purposes (including the setting up of a small business, the funding of the rent for some months, the funding of house equipment, and the coverage of medical expenses), already contemplating small financial plans after returning to home countries. In some cases, however, these plans are reversed upon return. Elene, who used the AVRR program a few months ago and is currently back in Georgia, points out that she had asked for several different alternatives of financial support (such as equipment for her apartment, the construction of a fence for a field, and the purchase of living stock since she had

previous work experience) but all of them were rejected. She expresses her frustration with the unsuccessful attempts to contact IOM in Georgia and with the equipment they finally decided to provide her, stressing that:

‘They (IOM) told me, “We will give you this small tractor, since you have land, and you have fields!”. We had no other choice, and they gave us no other options. [...] I guess that’s what they’re not selling (have as a stock) and that is why they are giving it to us. I don’t know what to say!’ (Elene, from Georgia, 19/4/2024).

Similarly, Mustafa, a 33-year-old Kurdish man, who is registered with AVRR and has applied for a refrigerator and a kitchen for his home in Iraq as a reintegration allowance, expresses great doubt as to whether he will eventually receive it on his return, citing rumours he has heard regarding IOM in the countries of return.

‘However, I have heard rumours of mismanagement of reintegration allowances in countries of return, where IOM offices operate. There are synergies between local IOM executives and specific shops/“known” service providers from which the IOM approves purchases and uses false receipts. In this way, the reintegration amount is divided among the three, the local IOM executive, the provider/shopkeeper and whatever is left is used by the beneficiary’ (Mustafa, Kurd from Iraq, 12/6/2024).

The management of the reintegration funding in the countries of return has been a thorny issue and one that has occasionally arisen sparked suspicions and discontent among our migrant informants. Although unconfirmed by our research, allegations concerning informal ‘deals’ or bribes (with local IOM officials in countries of return) or ‘synergies’ among the local IOM and specific shopkeepers have been voiced, raising questions about alternative ways of handling the reintegration funding.

Moreover, other types of ‘deals’ or blackmailing seem to emerge in particular narratives of AVRR experiences. Below, the AVRR procedure as experienced by Mohammad’s father and narrated by Mohammad from Pakistan settled in Greece since 2011 is presented. Mohammad refers to the way his father was received in the airport of Pakistan, especially by the airport or border officials.

‘R: With your father, when you both decided he would return, would you like to tell me a bit about that experience and especially about the IOM program—how did you both find it, how did he find it, and how easy was it?’

I: It was wonderful. I didn’t go with them because I was working at the time, but they picked him up in a taxi and took my father to Thivon Street. I went down to see him, actually, and a friend of mine, who had the day off, took my father to the airport. They had given him a bag, which said UN, I think—I don’t remember exactly—this specific bag to identify people travelling with this group. To set them apart from the others. When they took them to the airport, they also gave my father, I think, if I’m not mistaken, because I don’t remember very well, something over 500 euros for travel expenses. They gave my father this money, and they gave some money to the others, too. It was in envelopes, actually. I spoke with my father after he arrived, and he told me, “They gave me the money, they spoke very nicely, and they greeted us all the way to the plane”. So he went back safe, in a joyful way. My father, too. Then I was a little kid, but I decided he should leave

[to Pakistan] because back then, there was Golden Dawn; they were beating people, he couldn't... My father also had issues and couldn't... because of his age, he couldn't work heavy jobs, so he sold things around the streets, lighters, [...], things like that. And with the situation I saw back then, I told him, "It's better for you to leave, let me work, and you go back to the country. If I can manage, I'll bring my siblings here so they don't have to stay there; they can come here to work".

R: When did your father return? What year?

I: My father came to Greece in 2008, to Crete, and we sent him back after five years. He didn't have any documents, either. Yes, and I arranged for his return after I finished with the pink card.

R: And from the time he registered, when he applied to this program to return, until the moment he left—did a lot of time pass? Do you remember?

I: I think it was... About a month, maybe 40 days, if I'm not mistaken. It wasn't much, you know. It was very quick. He went with a friend of mine the first time, and they went to the Pakistani Embassy because my father didn't have a passport, he only had his ID from Pakistan. They needed to issue a document to confirm that 'no one is forcing me, I'm leaving with this group, returning to Pakistan, and I want to leave on my own'. They took this document to the IOM group, and they processed it. Maybe another paper as well, which said something like the exact day my father was supposed to return. His name was marked there with a marker, along with the date, and at the bottom, it said the time he had to be at the airport to leave. [...] After my father went, honestly, the people who saw him off were very nice, and they [...] him. But the bad part was that when my father arrived at the airport in Pakistan, they were asking for money. But some people there started arguing, saying, "This money was given to us by the (IOM) group, you have no right to take it from us. We came here because we went for a better future and found nothing. Now, we're back. You can't just arrest us", because in Pakistan, there's this thing that "you went to another country illegally, and the police will catch you. They must keep you locked up for six months; there's a fine..." But the people who had come back gathered and were saying, "We went for a better future, and now you're asking us for money".

R: Who was asking? Who was asking for the money back?

I: Down there, it was the police, as my father told me. Then, some of the others who were there, the younger guys, made a bit of a fuss, and they let them go. Because my father had that bag [the IOM bag], I think there's some agreement not to bother these people, they know we sent them... I think they even know about it down there. But they wanted some kind of tip [bribe, to take their money], and they were saying, "We'll scare them a bit and get some money". But in the end, they didn't give them anything. They told them, "We came here, we were sent by this specific group, you have no right to throw us in prison now. We didn't do anything; sure, we left illegally back then, but why didn't you catch us then? What's your business now?" So, finally, they let them go.

I: When I went to Pakistan for the first time with my residence permit, a police officer at the control point taking photos asked me, "What's your name?" I told him my name, then he asked, "When did you go to Greece?" I answered, "Such and such date". Then he asked how I went. I said, "How did I go? By plane" (jokingly, as he had left irregularly). I made a little joke. I told him, "I went by

plane. You don't know how people leave? Thousands left this country. How did they go, on foot. How did they leave from here?" He responded, "You talk too much". I told him, "My parents are waiting outside" (outside the airport where he arrived). After so many years, I came to Pakistan with a residence permit, with a passport. It's stamped, I'm legal. What you're doing right now, you don't even have the right to ask me how I went. I'm here now. You should have asked me then [back when I left]. If they're going to catch you now...you've spoken to those...' there is a group that questions people, asking if they left the country legally, if they had a visa or left illegally, and fines them. They were trying to scare me. So I told him, "Alright, I'll leave my suitcases with my parents, and you can hold me here for 10-13 years for leaving illegally. I spent 13 years in Greece, so you can hold me here for 13 years too". And he replied, "You talk too much". I told him, "Your job is to check. If the documents are fake, then take me in. I came here legally; you don't have..." All he was doing was trying to get a little bribe, but I know these things. So I told him, "Sir, please, it's not your job to ask me that. [...] Just stamp my entry that I came to Pakistan, as they did for me in Greece, smoothly and respectfully, with a stamp". There were other guys behind me who agreed with me, and we all said, "You're not doing the right thing", and they let us go. If you don't speak up, they say, "Alright, buy me a coffee or give me a little something". You understand? That's how these things go. This is what happens' (Mohammad, from Pakistan, 29/9/2024).

As Mohammad's vivid narrative illustrates, representatives of authorities in the country of return may blackmail returnees carrying the IOM bag (and the cash given to them by IOM Greece at the airport gate) by threatening them with arrest on the grounds of their irregular migration from Pakistan when they first fled. As Mohammad explained, this serves as a demonstration of power on the part of the authorities, mainly with the aim of extorting money from returnees, and consists a common practice.

4.5 Perceptions about migrating elsewhere

A small percentage of interviewees expressed desire to migrate elsewhere. This does not necessarily reflect the perceptions of migrants currently settled in the country, but is related to the specific research focus and the interviewees' selection¹⁰. Alma, from Albania, points out the differences between the first and second-generation migrants regarding the possibilities of moving to other European countries.

'For the second generation it will be migration to other countries rather than to Albania. [...] Albania is foreign to them. [...] The first generation will be caught between here and Albania' (Alma, from Albania, 14/3/2024).

For those who have expressed desire to migrate elsewhere, the movement is invested with expectations for more stability, better living conditions, more stable legal status, and access to education for them and their children. Perceptions of moving forward often stem from a

¹⁰First, this is due to the fact that a large percentage of participants (12 out of 30) were already enrolled in the AVRR and had already planned their return, which precludes at least a near term plan to migrate to another country. Second, long-term settled migrant interviewees, who have completed or are about to complete their working cycle in Greece, are more likely to follow return pathways, as highlighted in the previous chapter.

general dissatisfaction with working conditions, social benefit policies, and social integration processes in Greece. Below Hussain, from Pakistan, articulates his plan for further migration to Germany, highlighting the racism they experience in Greece as a key motivation for leaving.

'Because in Greece, we work like donkeys, you know that. We don't earn much. So, I plan, if my wife doesn't come, to move. I will move to Germany. If she comes, I will still fight for 2-3-4 years to get her paperwork sorted, for my children. [...] But we still have the same goal to leave from here. [...] The reasons are many. The first reason is racism. That's the primary reason. Second, no matter how hard I try, I don't get any respect. Because they still see me as black, of foreign origin, and I'm not beneficial to them. No matter how much life I give to Greece, I'm a migrant' (Hussain, from Pakistan, 30/9/2024).

The countries of Central and Northern Europe figure as the most attractive destinations in seeking better opportunities and prospects for them and their families. Interviewees refer to settlement experiences of their relatives and friends, with frequent references to living standards and career opportunities in Germany and Sweden. These experiences are contrasted with the lack of social benefits in Greece even after obtaining residence permit and with the obstacles to obtain citizenship. Karim, from Afghanistan, 38 years old, who came to Greece in 2001, illustrates the reasons why Germany is an attractive destination for Afghans.

'That is where it really applies that an asylum seeker or a recognized political refugee has equal rights as a German. [...] It really applies because I experienced it myself with some friends I have over there. [...]. In the third year they get German citizenship automatically. [...] When you start, you are already legal. Three years go by, you've worked, you've put in your stamps, you've settled in, you've integrated into German culture more or less, and it gives you that right. [...] With so many efforts that I put in, if I was in one of these countries back then, I would be a very strong politician today. I would have reached very high' (Karim, from Afghanistan, 9/4/2024).

However, the desire to migrate to another country also coexists with constrained expectations, awareness of the different challenges posed by different contexts, and the reality of the wider European migration policies. Elira, from Albania, underscores:

'Someday yes, I mean I'm thinking about going to some western countries in Europe, not because I'm going crazy for the west, but in a legislative framework and in an accessibility framework some things will be more ok. But not because the system is ok over there. The system is the same type of abusive everywhere, with a different flavour if you change the zip code a little bit. But at least you'll encounter different problems, which you'll find more tolerable' (Elira, from Albania, 17/10/2024).

4.6 Towards a typology of trajectories

Migration trajectories are multifaceted and dynamic, shaped by evolving political contexts, personal aspirations and positionalities, and diverse spatialities and temporalities. Thus, categorising these trajectories is inherently challenging, as any typology should preferably remain flexible and open to changes. This section discusses types of trajectories based on our

research, emphasising their non-exclusive and dynamic nature. These types of trajectories should be understood as fluid, acknowledging the limitations inherent in our study's methodological decisions, the constraints in the selection of interviewees, and the limitations deriving from the research focus on return migration.

In the following, we outline four types of trajectories that encapsulate particular decision-making processes, and perspectives on movement, return, and policy among migrants. In these, factors such as nationality, gender, age, socio-political and economic circumstances, and personal aspirations intersect in various ways. The intersections of nationality and legal status, however, emerge as a particularly significant driver. This is because migration and asylum policies in Greece and the European Union often categorize individuals based on nationality, influencing both their legal status and mobility. Such classifications may include distinctions between 'deserving' refugees and 'illegal' migrants, and decisions based on the concepts of 'safe country of origin', or 'safe third country', among others which may shift over time. Even if we refrain from such categorisations (Crawley and Skleparis, 2017), they are inevitably somehow reflected in the following types of trajectories.

The four types that emerged from the research are the following: i) *Seeking safety and dignity, no prospects of return*; ii) *Escaping decades of irregularity, circular routes, and aspirations for permanent return*; iii) *Processes of irregularisation, multi-directional mobilities*, iv) *Second generation, moving forward instead of returning*.

The first type refers mainly to beneficiaries of international protection—refugees who have fled war zones or oppressive regimes. A characteristic example is the Afghan refugees who lack any viable prospects for return to Afghanistan, primarily due to ongoing repression and pervasive human rights violations within the country's specific political context. Instead, their migration trajectories and aspirations reflect a pursuit of safety and dignity in new destinations. This type of trajectory also includes Syrian refugees and, to a lesser extent, Iraqis. Even in cases where Iraq is considered a 'safe country', a generalized sense of fear persists, further influencing their decision to seek better opportunities elsewhere. In many cases, even among those who arrived in Greece after 2015–2016, refugees decide to leave Greece, either during the asylum application process or after gaining recognition as refugees. This trend is driven by the limited integration opportunities available in Greece, which hinder the establishment of a secure and stable future.

The second type primarily refers to Georgian women who have lived and worked as undocumented migrants in Greece for decades. Many have returned to Georgia multiple times yet continue to engage in circular migration patterns in pursuit of livelihoods. This phenomenon underscores significant aspects of gendered migration, particularly prevalent in southern European countries since the 1990s. The majority of migrants in this type are women approaching retirement age who have been working as domestic workers. Precarious employment, as well as the undocumented status even after many years of residence in Greece, left them unable to secure labour or retirement rights. As they reach older age, many express a desire or feel compelled to return to their country of origin. However, their migration journeys are often marked by repeated returns to Greece due to challenges encountered in their home country. These repeated movements are frequently shaped by the temporal limitations of visa regimes, which allow a stay of up to 90 days in Greece, followed by mandatory return to Georgia before migrating again. Similar patterns were observed among interviewees from Moldova and the Philippines, highlighting the transnational and gendered dimensions of these migration trajectories.

As regards the third type, this concerns mainly single men predominantly from Pakistan, who represent a category characterized by multi-directional mobilities, as reflected in many of our interviews. This type includes both documented and undocumented migrants, often alternating between periods of regular and irregular status. Having worked hard in Greece, those who obtain residence permits typically aim to return temporarily to Pakistan to visit or make family. Permanent return to Pakistan is not among the plans of those with stable employment and with secure legal status. Instead, they often aspire to move to other EU countries, expecting to improve their living conditions and prospects. Conversely, migrants unable to secure work or legal documentation, even after many years of employment and residence in the country, particularly those facing aging or health challenges, may view return as a viable option. Legal status, thus, among health and employment plays a role in shaping mobility aspirations. The decision to return, at least for the elderly ones, often constitutes a family decision, as their children who may also have migrated and continue to reside in Greece undertake the burden of supporting the family. For such individuals, programs like Assisted Voluntary Return and Reintegration (AVRR) provide a structured pathway for returning to Pakistan.

As for the fourth type, our interviews revealed distinct differences in mobility aspirations between the first and the second generation. While parents may plan to return to their countries of origin, their children often set their sights on other European countries, typically in Western or Northern Europe. Their aspirations and motivations align more closely with those of their peers who grew up in Greece, including native-born individuals; albeit marked by experiences of racism and/or discrimination. This comparison highlights the influence of socio-cultural and economic factors experienced during their upbringing in Greece, which shape their aspirations and migration goals in a different way from those of their parents.

5. Conclusion

The Country Dossier examined migrants' experiences in Greece, focusing on mobility trajectories, shifting aspirations, social integration, mainly as regard the 'pre-return phase', including migrants who are found in the 'spectrum of risk of return' either today or in the near future, and trajectories encompassing both forced and assisted voluntary returns, viewed as part of a continuum of coercion rather than a strict dichotomy (Sahin-Mencutek and Triandafyllidou, 2024; Papatzani et al., forthcoming).

The findings revealed the multiplicity of trajectories, factors, networks, and social, economic and political circumstances shaping migrants experiences. First, mobilities and movements, including returns, are rarely linear processes. Instead, migration trajectories often encompass diverse and complex patterns, such as multiple returns to countries of origin for temporary visits for family, usually for those obtaining residence permits. Such returns may be followed by re-migration to Greece, even for migrants that returned through the AVRR program. For others, including migrant women living irregularly in Greece for decades, circular movements may be currently the main mobility pattern, the temporalities of which are defined by visa restrictions.

The reasons for the aforementioned mobility patterns from those already undertaking them are diverse. Notably, the economic crisis of the 2010s intensified return or aspirations of moving further and reshaped migration pathways. The socio-political context in Greece has been also a crucial factor, especially regarding the multiple manifestations of racism not only at the institutional level, but also through violent practices, including far-right violence that emerged in parallel with the rise of the neo-Nazi organisation Golden Dawn.

Moreover, the social and economic context of settlement and integration in Greece, as determined by the governance of migration, has affected previous mobilities and impacts on perceptions and future aspirations. Intersecting experiences of irregularisation and labour as well as legal precarity have evolved significantly over recent decades, profoundly affecting migrants in Greece. These include the further normalisation of undeclared labour, particularly for undocumented migrants, growing anxieties about pensions, housing marginalisation, and access to essential services and their impact on migrants' ability to support their families. Challenges in issuing or renewing residence permits exacerbate these precarious conditions, limiting migrants' mobility and prompting some to consider leaving Greece despite their informal integration networks. Exclusionary policies rooted in institutional racism further intensify these struggles, manifesting in policing, detention, forced removals, and routine street arrests. Such experiences, that may often be repeated for migrants, as well as the fear and threat thereof shape migrants' everyday lives and mobility decisions.

Local relationships and networks play a crucial role in shaping migrants' everyday experiences in Greece, particularly in urban neighbourhoods. These connections, ranging from mutual support to prejudice, often mitigate systemic integration barriers and challenge traditional notions of citizenship. However, tensions persist, as racism and xenophobia continue to influence interactions and public life. Family and friends significantly impact migrants' settlement and mobility, with local networks sometimes providing more support than transnational ties. Migrant organisations also play a vital role in offering education, legal assistance, and advocacy for labour rights, while many engage in political activism, especially around anti-racist, feminist, and labour issues.

Migrants' perceptions of returning to their countries of origin are shaped by a combination of economic, social, and political factors in both their home countries and Greece. Political instability, security concerns, and human rights violations, particularly for migrants from

Afghanistan or those with queer identities, are significant barriers. Economic challenges and cultural shifts from long settlement in Greece also deter return, as do changes in migrants' aspirations. Other factors shaping the unwillingness to return relate to the migrants' -and their families'- expectations and perspectives on perceived failures and success related to migration. Additionally, personal factors such as family obligations, aging, health issues, and the desire to reunite with loved ones, alongside economic hardship, irregular status, and fears of detention and racist violence in Greece, further influence the decision to stay or return. Others wish to migrate further, usually towards western and northern European countries, as has been already done in case of many asylum seekers and recognised beneficiaries of international protection since 2015. Such perceptions are driven by hopes for greater stability, improved living conditions, more secure legal status, and better access to education for themselves and their children.

Policy Recommendations

When asked about any recommendations that would improve the current situation in Greece, Ahmed, from Pakistan, replied by bringing to the fore the issue of detainees in relation to the recent legislation providing residence permits to cover existing labour shortages.

'And the people who do not have asylum or anything, they put them in jail. Why are they not taking them out? And also herethere is a need [for labour] and they are giving visa to the [nationals of] other countries to come here for work. You [should] take out that people [from the detention centres] and give them permanent residence and they will be working here! It's good for you, you do not need to bring in other people! [...] These other people, who are coming from other countries with the visa ok, even they don't know the language, even they don't know your law, everything. [But] that person who is in the prison here, he already knows the law, he knows the language, he knows the work. Because he's been working here for maybe two years. He knows something about that work. It's easy for you [the government]' (Ahmed, from Pakistan, 2/6/2024).

The quote above highlights a key paradox in recent years. The state's efforts to regularize migrants to address labour shortages contrast sharply with the poor living and working conditions (detention, camp isolation, lack of integration opportunities, etc.) imposed by the same authorities. These conditions have led asylum seekers and refugees to leave the country in search of better opportunities, thereby contributing to the labour shortages that the state is simultaneously trying to address. As the analysis in the present Country Dossier indicates, it is primarily the conditions in Greece that drive individuals to consider further movements, either returning to their home countries or migrating to other EU states. Therefore, policy recommendations should prioritize improving the overall living and integration conditions for migrants and refugees in Greece.

Improve reception and accommodation conditions:

Improvements should begin with the reception and accommodation system for asylum applicants, prior to integration. This includes ensuring dignified, fair, and thorough treatment of asylum cases. The emphasis should be on individualized procedures that align with human

rights, rather than simply accelerating asylum processing through massive rejection of applications.

Reinstate urban housing programs:

Crucial changes are needed in the accommodation of asylum applicants. The recent termination of the ESTIA housing program has led to a shift towards camp-based reception systems (Kandylis, Papatzani, and Polyzou, 2024), reinforcing marginalisation rather than combating it. This shift, alongside previous shortcomings, has resulted in accommodation policies that fail to address isolation, segregation, and exclusion in refugee camps. To improve conditions, an urban housing program should be reinstated in cities, providing dignified living spaces for asylum seekers. Such improvements are essential as they shape asylum seekers' first interactions with the Greek migration system, influencing their prospects for settlement and integration.

Improve the overall living and integration conditions:

Integration opportunities for beneficiaries of international protection and migrants should be significantly enhanced across various sectors, including labour, education, healthcare, and access to services. The lack of these opportunities in recent years has led many recognized beneficiaries of international protection to leave Greece informally for other EU countries. Improving integration should also involve providing housing for the most vulnerable and reconsidering the termination of the HELIOS program, run by IOM which, even as a pilot initiative, offered essential services such as housing assistance (IOM, 2024b). The urgent implementation of a national integration policy is needed to address emerging needs and support long-term settlement.

Facilitate residence permits regulations:

Regulations regarding residence permits, particularly high fees and strict criteria even for long-established migrants, should be reconsidered in order to secure the residence rights of settled migrants, combat precarious employment associated with irregular status, and address the consequences of irregularisation (Papatzani et al., 2024). Ensuring regular migration routes must also be prioritized.

Reconsider the use of detention, respect detainees' rights:

Moreover, detention is extensively and arbitrarily used in various cases, even for applicants of international protection and migrants who have registered for AVRR. Apart from respecting detainees' rights and dignity, ensuring their access to legal representation, and eliminating detention in police stations, the Greek administration has to revise the use of detention altogether, making sure that detention is the last 'resort' and alternatives to detention are effectively implemented (Hatziprokopiou et al., 2024).

Improve the legal framework on returns:

Regarding return policies, the coexistence of multiple legal frameworks with divergent procedures that undermine the implementation of the Return Directive should be reconsidered. Greece should adopt only the standards of the Law transposing the Return Directive (Hatziprokopiou et al., 2024). Additionally, changes are needed in the routine police practice of issuing return or deportation orders to TCNs who enter irregularly but later apply for international protection and are granted a permit to stay. The immediate cessation of pushbacks is essential.

Improve AVRR, separate AVRR from detention:

For those considering return, the AVRR program offers a more dignified alternative. However, to establish it as a genuinely voluntary option, authorities and relevant actors should separate AVRR from detention by: i) ensuring that individuals are released from detention upon registration for the program, and ii) refraining from arresting those with documentation confirming their participation (Papatzani et al., forthcoming). Additionally, AVRR should be offered primarily to individuals living autonomously, rather than those in large facilities like reception and accommodation camps, especially if they are in vulnerable psychosocial states after difficult migration journeys. This practice undermines individuals' intentions to seek asylum or their need for protection. Furthermore, requiring individuals to refrain from regular status or asylum applications to be eligible for AVRR should be a last resort and implemented in a way –and at a time– that ensures no protection gaps. Finally, the financial assistance for reintegration and return should be reconsidered and increased to account for rising living costs in return countries. The disparity in financial aid between those living on the Greek mainland and those on the islands should also be addressed to ensure equal treatment of AVRR beneficiaries.

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Annexes

1. GAPs WP7 Interview Guide

Note: Interviewer to fill out

Interview date:

Location:

Duration:

Language:

General identification questions:

- Nationality (multiple origins, passports)
- Age
- Gender
- Social background
- Regional origin (within the country such as rural or urban)
- Educational background
- Civic status (such as married, single etc.)
- Family situation (such as separated; living transnational lives/ transnational partnership/family relation, single mother/father)
- Support for (kids, family...)
- Religious belonging (if available)
- Ethnic belonging/minority (if available)
- Date of arrival at the respective country (year)
- Legal status (Asylum seeker, International protection, Subsidiary protection, Temporary protection, Naturalization/citizenship)

Presentation of the interview

Hello Sir/Madam, my name is _____ I'm currently working at the national Centre for Social Research. Thank you for agreeing to take some of your time to talk to us.

The project for which we will be conducting an interview with you today is related to the life experiences and goals of migrants. The aim of our research is to understand how migrants in transit countries (pre-return phase) consider, decide, and communicate decisions about return in the context of broader im/mobility experiences.

Our talk should take around 45 minutes to 1 hour. I will be asking you some questions but if you have any hesitations or inquiries during the interview, feel free to express them.

(Consent information provided) I would like to point out that your answers will remain anonymous and that our discussion will remain confidential, you will be given a pseudonym name to assure that information will remain unidentifiable when the research findings are published.

You have the freedom to stop the interview at any point without giving a reason or explanation.

Thank participant for his/her time

Any questions or comments before we start?

Ask for permission to record audio

4.1 Agency and social navigation

In this section of the interview, we want to know about your choices, goals and decisions that you have made now and in the past, both about migration to [country] and in terms of your life

in general. We also want to know about your plans for the future in terms of migrating and for your life in general.

1. Please describe the important decisions or choices you made for your life in the past in terms of where to live and where to move to. What were the reasons behind taking the decision to leave a city or country in the past? How do you make important life decisions about leaving or staying today? What helps you to decide and what are your goals? Why/how come are you in [current country of residence]? Where did you want to move? Do you still want to move there [if not first choice]? How do you evaluate your decisions now - are you proud/ashamed, satisfied/worried, etc.? Would you make any decision differently now based on what you now know?
2. Were there particular information or resources you had that made the move possible or easy? Who do you talk to and get information or advice from? What are the main factors that you consider and why?
3. With whom did you move? Are there some members who did not move/or moved elsewhere around the same time as you? [If so, to what do you attribute their decisions/experiences to not move or move elsewhere?]
4. How do you feel about possibly staying here or leaving? Why do you want to stay here / leave here? When you think about this place, what comes to mind?
5. Have you or others (family members, friends, etc.?) attempted / looked into the possibilities of further moves? Why (yes/no)? If so, where? (third country? Return?)
6. Please describe your plans, dreams, or hopes for the future. What do you hope to accomplish in the next chapter of your life? What do you think will happen (in any area of your life) in the future?

4.2 Social networks, family and institutions

In this section of the interview, we want to know about the people - friends, family or social groups - that are important to you, especially as this relates to the places that you have lived and may think of living in the future.

1. Tell me about your friends, family members here and in other countries/cities. Where are they and what are they doing? How often do you contact/see them? How close do you feel to them? What do they tell you about the life where they live?
2. What type of obligations (if any) do you have to help or care for particular relatives or friends in this country or in other countries? How do you feel about this?
3. What do you see in your future in terms of serious life relationships or partnerships/children? What do you hope for?
4. Are you involved in diaspora and migrant organisations?
 - What role do they play in your experience in this country?
 - Please describe them (these could be a range of organisations, including activist/solidarity groups, etc.)
 - How did you reach them and decide to get involved?
 - Are they involved in your decision-making process regarding your life trajectory? (if so, please explain)
 - Do they provide any information? (if so, please explain)

4.3 Integration context- livelihood and socio-cultural context

In this section of the interview, we want you to tell us about how you are feeling about where you live now, how you feel about your life here [in the current country of residence] .

1. Where do you live in this city, what is it like and do you feel at home? How do you feel about being in this place? (safe, deportable, at risk, ...) what makes you feel that way?
2. Do you feel wanted/unwanted by the host population? by the state? Did that change over time? How?
3. Tell me about your daily life, how are you spending your time? What type of work do you do? Have you accessed any education here? Do you work (and if so, where, what is it like)? Have you learned the language? Do you have any friends who are locals? What are neighbours like?
4. What types of challenges do you face? (discrimination, livelihood, health, work conditions) What is the current public opinion in this country about migrants from your country? How do you feel about this?
5. How is this place in comparison to other places you have been? To what extent do you feel like you belong in these different places?
6. Please tell the story of how your religious, moral, and/or political views and values have developed over time. Have they changed in any important ways? Please explain. (sensitive question, omit if necessary)

4.4 Changing landscapes of governance, borders and institutions

In this section of the interview, we want to know how you have been affected by laws and policies made by the state (and in particular as these affect where you live or your future plans about where to go).

1. How involved are you in politics of your current host country? How involved are you in politics of your country of origin? Have you heard about policies regarding migrants? What/How? As far as you know, who decides what happens about/to migrants in this country (i.e. government, international agencies, EU)? What are the policies affecting you in the place where you are now? Would you be allowed to stay here longer-term if you want to? What are the restrictions you face? What are the policies in places you would consider moving to (ideally)?
2. What do you know about return policies? How do these political changes and policies impact on how you feel about your current place of residence? On your decisions about migration or return?
3. If you chose to migrate elsewhere, what are the conditions under which you would do so? If you chose to do so in the future, how would you go (i.e. land/air/sea; alone/with others; smugglers)?
4. Would you ever go back to your country of origin? Under what conditions (if any) would you feel you could go back? What is the situation like in your country of origin for returnees? How are returnees perceived by people there? What are the risks and dangers of going back to you personally or to members of your family? When you think about returning, what thoughts, feelings or words come to mind?
5. Are you aware of any programmes or organizations that could help you to migrate onward or return? If so, what do you know about them and how did you learn about them?

Last Question: What should programs or organizations offer to facilitate a possible return?

2. List of WP7 Interviews

N.	Interview ID	Pseudonym	Country of Origin	Date of arrival to Greece	Legal Status & Mobility	Gender	Age	Work situation
1	GAPs_GRmigrant1_2024	Alma	Albania	1994	Citizenship	F	60	Unemployed
2	GAPs_GRmigrant2_2024	Tamar	Georgia	2001	Undocumented, two times returned to Georgia	F	60	Domestic worker
3	GAPs_GRmigrant3_2024	Karim	Afghanistan	2001	Residence permit, Further attempts towards EU	M	38	Carpenter
4	GAPs_GRmigrant4_2024	Ali	Pakistan	2014	Residence permit	M	31	Employed in open grocery markets
5	GAPs_GRmigrant5_2024	Elene	Georgia	2003	Undocumented, returned through AVRR.	F	70	Domestic worker for 20 years in Greece, currently retired in Georgia.
6	GAPs_GRmigrants6_2024	Ana	Moldova	2007	Citizenship	F	25	Graduate student
7	GAPs_GRmigrant7_2024	Salome	Georgia	2016	Former asylum seeker in Greece, enrolled in AVRR	F	44	Domestic worker
8	GAPs_GRmigrant8_2024	Khalid	Iraq	2000	Residence permit	M	44	Employed
9	GAPs_GRmigrant9_2024	Tamer	Egypt	2006	Residence permit	M		Employed
10	GAPs_GRmigrant10_2024	Reza	Iran (Kurd)	2023	Rejected asylum applicant	M	28	Employed
11	GAPs_GRmigrant11_2024	Ahmed	Pakistan	2018/08	Rejected asylum applicant	M	28	Employed
12	GAPs_GRmigrant12_2024	Mariam	Georgia	2011	Undocumented, enrolled in OCAVRR	F	38	Unemployed
13	GAPs_GRmigrant13_2024	Andrea	Philippines	1989	Undocumented, enrolled in OCAVRR	F	70	Retired with no pension
14	GAPs_GRmigrant14_2024	Ismael	Burundi	2021	Rejected asylum applicant, enrolled in OCAVRR	M	32	Unemployed
15	GAPs_GRmigrant15_2024	Leila	Lebanon (Palestinian)	2024	Enrolled in OCAVRR	F	70	Unemployed
16	GAPs_GRmigrant16_2024	Mustafa	Iraq/Kurdistan	2024 (April)	Asylum seeker, enrolled in OCAVRR	M	33	Unemployed
17	GAPs_GRmigrant17_2024	Hassan	Pakistan	2017	Undocumented, enrolled in OCAVRR	M	40	Employed

18	GAPs_GRmigrant18_2024	Arjun	India	2020	Undocumented, enrolled in OCAVRR	M	30	Unemployed
19	GAPs_GRmigrant19_2024	Omar	Pakistan	2023	Undocumented, enrolled in OCAVRR	M	27	Unemployed
20	GAPs_GRmigrant20_2024	Farhan	Pakistan	2016	Undocumented, enrolled in OCAVRR	M	28	Unemployed
21	GAPs_GRmigrant21_2024	Usman	Pakistan	2004	Residence permit, enrolled in OCAVRR	M	55	Unemployed
22	GAPs_GRmigrant22_2024	Nino	Georgia	2009	Undocumented	F	58	Elderly care giver
23	GAPs_GRmigrant23_2024	Larisa	Moldavia	1999	Citizenship	F	70	Elderly care giver/domestic house keeper
24	GAPs_GRmigrant24_2024	Irina	Georgia	1997	Residence permit	F	64	Elderly care giver
25	GAPs_GRmigrant25_2024	Zaid	Pakistan	2017	Rejected asylum applicant, applied for the new law	M	24	Employed at an NGO
26	GAPs_GRmigrant26_2024	Mohammad	Pakistan	2011	Residence permit	M	29	Seasonal worker at Kos, cook
27	GAPs_GRmigrant27_2024	Hussain	Pakistan	2010	Residence permit	M	33	Seasonal worker at Santorini, two jobs
28	GAPs_GRmigrant28_2024	Elira	Albania	2018	Residence permit	queer	22	Student
29	GAPs_GRmigrant29_2024	Bledar	Albania	1992	Expatriate identity card	M	78	Retired
30	GAPs_GRmigrant30_2024	Rahim	Bangladesh	2019	Residence permit (new Law)	M	33	Employed

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